

India-Japan Symposium On Emerging Technologies
October 7, 2010
Indian Embassy Auditorium, Tokyo, Japan

Program and Abstract Book

Organized by
Indian Scientists Association in Japan (ISAJ)

Supported by
Embassy of India

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डा. आर. चिदम्बरम्

भारत सरकार के प्रमुख वैज्ञानिक सलाहकार
एवम्

डी.ए.इ. - होमी भाभा प्रोफेसर

Dr. R. Chidambaram

Principal Scientific Adviser to the Govt. of India
&

DAE - Homi Bhabha Professor

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MESSAGE

I am delighted to learn that the Indian Scientists Association in Japan (ISAJ) is organizing this "India-Japan Symposium on Emerging Technologies" in Tokyo. I was present at the inaugural ceremony of ISAJ early last year and am impressed by the strides it has taken since then.

We have always admired the remarkable progress of Japan after the ravages of World War II and this has been driven by Science and Technology. The technology foresight analyses carried out by MITI in those days helped Japan to make the right choices of technologies, in which they could become global innovation leaders. More recently they have also established some of the best facilities in the world for basic research.

India also is now on a path of rapid economic growth and it has an exceptional reservoir of human resource. Cooperation in Science and Technology between India and Japan, I am therefore convinced, will be mutually beneficial and this is what will make it sustainable over a long period of time. The present Symposium is an important step in that direction.

R. Chidambaram

(R. Chidambaram)

10th September, 2010

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VI Floor, Central Complex, Trombay, Mumbai - 400085

AMBASSADOR OF INDIA
TOKYO

16 September, 2010

MESSAGE

I am happy to learn that the Indian Scientists Association in Japan (ISAJ) is organizing a India-Japan Symposium on Emerging Technologies.

Since its inauguration last year, ISAJ has become a registered NPO in Japan. I congratulate ISAJ members on their achievements.

The issues being covered in the symposium are highly topical and relevant. Considering the growing, multi-faceted partnership between Japan and India, I have no doubt that the symposium will lead to greater collaboration among scientists of both countries in the years ahead.

I convey my best wishes for the success of the ISAJ symposium.

[H.K. Singh]

Message

I extend my heartfelt congratulations to all of you for holding the India-Japan Symposium on Emerging Technologies organized by the Indian Scientists Association in Japan and supported by the Embassy of India in Japan. India is one of the most important partners of Japan not only in Economy and Industry but also in Science and Technology. I believe this symposium is a clear proof of continuous enlargement of the relationship between Japan and India in science and technology.

In collaboration with India, we have implemented the research exchange type of “Strategic International Cooperative Program” with the Department of Science and Technology (DST) of India since 2006. Through this program, JST and DST have jointly supported Japanese-Indian collaborative research projects in the field of “Multidisciplinary Research Field, which combines Information and Communications Technology with Other Fields”. In another international collaborative program “Science and Technology Research Partnership for Sustainable Development”, we have been supporting Japanese-Indian collaborative research projects in the field of environment/energy and natural disaster prevention in collaboration with Japan International Cooperation Agency (JICA).

The Indian scientists in Japan play significant roles in promoting bilateral collaborations. Moreover, I am grateful to our Indian collaborators and the Embassy of India for their unstinting supports. I hope that cooperation between Japan and India in the field of science and technology will continue to flourish and expand in the future and I believe India will grow as a more and more important partner for us.

Sincerely,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Koichi Kitazawa', written in a cursive style.

Dr. Koichi Kitazawa

President

Japan Science and Technology Agency

Indian Scientists Association in Japan (ISAJ)

Convener's Welcome

I, on behalf of the Organizing Committee, warmly welcome the guests and all the delegates to the India-Japan Symposium on Emerging Technologies.

This symposium is being organized by the Indian Scientists Association in Japan (ISAJ). ISAJ was conceived and formed at the end of 2008 by coming together of many Indian researchers working in Japan. It was then formally inaugurated by Prof. R. Chidambaram, Principal Scientific Adviser to Government of India in January 2009, in the presence of His Excellency the Ambassador of India to Japan, Mr. Hemant Krishan Singh. ISAJ is now registered as a Non Profit Organization (NPO) in Japan.

The major aim of ISAJ is to give opportunities for Indian and Japanese scientists/researchers to interact and exchange scientific ideas and information on the scientific advances in emerging areas of science and technology. This symposium is being organized as a small step toward achieving such goal.

This is our first symposium, featuring over 91 speakers giving 11 plenary lectures, 14 oral presentations, 60 poster presentations and 6 panelists. It is a great opportunity for networking amongst scientists of both countries and to build the foundation for future scientific research collaboration, with the view of promoting India-Japan scientific cooperation.

The Embassy of India (Tokyo), Dr. Pankajakshan Thadathil, S&T Counsellor, in particular, has been the core supporter of ISAJ right from its conception and progress. The Symposium would not have been possible without the generous support of the Embassy of India.

I gratefully acknowledge the major sponsorship from the Bank of India and New India Assurance.

Finally, I thank you, all our guests who have taken time out of your busy schedule to attend this important meeting. Your active participation is the key to the success of this symposium.

On behalf of the organizing committee, I extend a very warm welcome to all the participants and wish you all a very productive and memorable symposium. I sincerely hope that the symposium will challenge and inspire, and result in collaborations and friendships between the scientists/researchers from our two nations.

With best regards,

Sunil Kaul
Symposium Convener & Chairman
ISAJ

India - Japan Symposium on Emerging Technologies
October 7, 2010 (Thursday)
Indian Embassy Auditorium, Tokyo
PROGRAM

8:00 - 9:00		Registration
9:00 - 10:10		Inaugural Session
9:00 - 9:10	Welcome Address	Dr. Sunil Kaul <i>Chairman, ISAJ</i>
9:10 - 9:20	Opening Remarks	<i>His Excellency</i> Mr. Hemant Krishan Singh <i>Indian Ambassador to Japan</i>
9:20 - 9:35	Inauguration and Inaugural Address	Shri Prithviraj Chavan <i>Honorable Minister of State Science & Technology and Earth Sciences Government of India</i>
9:35 - 9:45	Keynote Address	Mr. Itaru Watanabe <i>Dy. Director General, MEXT</i>
9:45 - 10:05	India - Japan Science and Technology collaboration: past, present and future	Dr. Pankajakshan Thadathil <i>Science Counsellor Embassy of India, Tokyo</i>
10:05 - 10:10	Vote of Thanks	Dr. Kedar Mahapatra <i>General Secretary, ISAJ</i>
10:10 - 10:15	Group Photo	
10:15 - 10:35	Tea Break	
10:35 - 11:35		Plenary Session 1 Earth Sciences & Space Technology
	Chair: Prof. Keitaro Yoshihara <i>Chairman of India-Japan Science Council</i>	
10:35 - 10:55	Toshio Yamagata	<i>Climate variations and their impact on society</i>
10:55 - 11:15	Swadhin Behera	<i>Evolving research interests in the Indian ocean climate</i>
11:15 - 11:35	<u>Short Presentations</u> (4 Presentations, 5 min each)	
	J. Venkata Ratnam	<i>El Niño Modoki in the equatorial pacific and the anomalous climatic conditions during the summer and winters of 2009-10</i>
	Hirotsada Moki	<i>Estimation of zooplankton biomass in deep sea using new ocean carbon circulation model with additional plankton functional groups</i>
	Vinu Valsala	<i>Bottom-up and top-down approaches estimated that the global ocean sinks as large as ~ 2 gigatonne grams of carbon on each year from the atmosphere</i>

	Sudha Radhika	<i>Wind disaster detection from satellite and aerial imageries using wavelet feature extraction and latest pattern recognition techniques</i>
11:35 - 12:25	Plenary Session 2 Information & Communication Technology	
	Chair: Prof. Shiro Sakata <i>Department of Informatics and Imaging Systems, Chiba University</i>	
11:35 - 11:55	Norio Shiratori & Kazuo Hashimoto	<i>Towards symbiosis between human and nature via information communication - 'Kurihara' Green Project -</i>
11:55 - 12:15	Goutam Chakraborty & Glenn M. Keeni	<i>The good, the bad, the ugly and ubiquity</i>
12:15 - 12:25	<u>Short Presentations</u> (2 Presentations, 5 min each)	
	Ratna Krishnamoorthy	<i>REDEFINE: A GPP-reconfigurable architecture hybrid</i>
	Samik Ghosh	<i>A collaborative computational platform for curation and enrichment of biological pathways</i>
12:25 - 13:00	Lunch	
13:00 - 14:15	Poster Session & Free Interactions	
14:15 - 15:15	Plenary Session 3 Biotechnology & Agriculture	
	Chair: Prof. Renu Wadhwa <i>National Institute of Advanced Industrial Science & Technology (AIST), Tsukuba</i>	
14:15 - 14:35	Osamu Ito	<i>Indo - Japan cooperation for agricultural research in semi-arid tropics</i>
14:35 - 14:55	Guntur Subbarao	<i>Nitrification - A strategic point of intervention to limit nitrogen losses from agricultural systems?</i>
14:55 - 15:15	<u>Short Presentations</u> (4 Presentations, 5 min each)	
	Rumani Singh	<i>CARF- A novel regulator of cell proliferation</i>
	Baiju G. Nair	<i>Nanoparticles in ethnic medicines of India</i>
	Raghunadha Reddy Burri	<i>The effect of bound water molecules on binding orientations in CDK2 inhibitors</i>
	Kaliaperumal Venkatesh	<i>Study of mitochondrial physiology using Raman spectroscopy</i>
15:15 - 15:35	Tea Break	

15:35 - 17:15		Plenary Session 4 Energy & Materials
	Chair: Prof. An-Pang TSAI <i>Institute of Multidisciplinary Research for Advanced Materials (IMRAM) Tohoku University, Sendai</i>	
15:35 - 15:55	Kaneaki Tsuzaki	<i>Advances in structural metals for society and environment</i>
15:55 - 16:15	Alok Singh	<i>Novel approaches to strengthening of magnesium alloys for structural application</i>
16:15 - 16:45	<u>Short Presentations</u>	<i>(5 Presentations)</i>
	Pavuluri Srinivasu	<i>Nanostructured materials for electrochemical cells</i>
	Parasharam Shirage	<i>Iron isotope effect in Fe-based superconductors</i>
	Asima Sultana	<i>Development of uber catalytic NOx reduction technologies for diesel engines</i>
	Mrinmay Mukhopadhyay	<i>Indian Beamline at Photon Factory</i>
	Satoshi Konishi	<i>Energy education in Kyoto University under global COE program</i>
17:00 - 17:45		Panel Discussion Moderator: Prof. Swadhin Behera
	<u>Panelists:</u>	
	Geng Tu	<i>Department of International Affairs Japan Science and Technology Agency (JST)</i>
	Asuka Tsuboike	<i>Strategic Planning Division Japan International Cooperation Agency (JICA)</i>
	Keitaro Yoshihara	<i>India-Japan Science Council Faculty & Graduate School of Urban Environmental Sciences</i>
	Akie Hoshino	<i>Asian/African Program Division Japan Society for the Promotion of Science (JSPS)</i>
	Ruby Pawankar	<i>Nippon Medical School/ World Allergy Organization</i>
	Pankajakshan Thadathil	<i>Embassy of India, Tokyo</i>

PLENARY SESSION

ABSTRACTS

2010

India-Japan Science & Technology collaboration: Past, Present and Future

Pankajakshan Thadathil

Counsellor of Science & Technology

Embassy of India, Tokyo

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Historically, India and Japan have deep rooted links through the oriental culture and religion. In the past, we could not translate such cultural link to its full potential in improving India-Japan cooperation in any sector. However, during the recent years, there have been very significant improvements in the India-Japan partnership that eventually reflects in all sectors, including science and technology (S&T). A bilateral S&T Agreement between the two countries was signed in November 1985. With a view to provide more focus and purpose to S&T cooperation between the two countries, a Science and Technology Initiative to support pure science research in frontier areas of S&T has been proposed in 2005. The new Science and Technology Initiative have become successful in promoting substantial cooperation in the emerging areas of modern biology, biotechnology, health care, agriculture, hydrocarbon fuels, nano-science and nano-technology, environment, information and communication technology, robotics, alternative sources of energy etc. Under the new science and technology policy and also in the new growth strategy of Japan, two major innovations have been projected as the national strategic pillar. These are “green innovation” and “life innovation”. Under the national action plan on climate change, India is committed for the green innovation. Regarding life innovation, India is a world leader in generic medicine and there are world class R&D institutions engaged in life sciences. Considering the growing, multi-faceted partnership between Japan and India, it is important for both the nations to strengthen research partnership in these areas of common interest through close interaction between research organizations/institutions and scientists of both the countries. It’s also important to formulate strategy to cultivate the next generation of scientists and scholars from both countries who could move forward sustaining partnership between our two nations.

PL-02

Climate Variations and Their Impact on Society

Toshio Yamagata

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The intensely hot summer of this year and the cold winter of last year in Japan are examples of the extremes in the climate variation. Climate variation refers to a situation in which, due to various internal factors, climate fluctuates significantly around the normal state from seasons to decades. This is much different from climate change a situation in which the normal climate state changes over a longer period of time. Since intense heat and heavy snows are included among day-to-day meteorological phenomena, there will be cooler days in the heat of summer, and rays of sunshine amid the heavy snows. If these natural variations differ significantly from normal years over the season as a whole, they could justifiably be called climate variation.

The summer conditions for example are associated with such a processes related to climate variation. From around April, the sun reaches a high elevation near Indonesia, stimulating convection activity there. Warm air rises, and then falls near the Philippines. The resultant fine weather over waters near the Philippines causes seawater temperatures to rise significantly there. Then, in around July, the center of convection activity moves to this warmed sea region. The region of falling warm air moves northwards in tandem, until the region near Japan is covered with the Bonin (Ogasawara) high, ushering in the summer. This is called the atmospheric Pacific-Japan (PJ) pattern by the late Professor T. Nitta of Tokyo University. El Niño is a phenomenon that interrupts this seasonal progression and causes cool summer in Japan. When this phenomenon occurs, the warm seawater near the Philippines moves toward the region between the eastern Pacific and the International Date Line, making strong convection less likely to occur. The Bonin (Ogasawara) high that brings summer to Japan is not reinforced, either. On the other hand, it has become clear that, if the Indian Ocean Dipole Mode phenomenon occurs in the Indian Ocean, convection becomes active over the region ranging from northern India to near the Philippines. In that case, temperatures in Japan are extremely high. Models to predict climate variation first need to resolve those rich climate phenomena.

The state of human health, food production and the state of the earth environment are highly dependent on nature. Those are extremely vulnerable to risks due to climate variations under the stress of the global warming. Initiatives aimed at predicting climate variation have been progressing rapidly in professional climate science community. We are at a level whereby the occurrence of El Niño can be predicted one or two years in advance. By analyzing prediction data together with in situ data, we will not only deepen our understanding of predictability of climate variations but also improve parameterization schemes for cloud and precipitation processes to reduce climate model biases. I believe that those efforts will also contribute to deeper understanding of the unique evolution of our habitable aqua-planet.

PL-03

Evolving Research Interests in the Indian Ocean Climate

Swadhin Behera^{1,2}, Jing-Jia Luo^{1,2}, Yukio Masumoto^{1,3}, Toshio Yamagata^{2,3}

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The tropical oceans give rise to modes of climate variations that have large impacts on the human society. For example, the El Nino/Southern Oscillation (ENSO) of the tropical Pacific Ocean is one such phenomenon that causes widespread disasters, loss of human lives and economic losses of billions of dollars. The Indian Ocean was thought to be inept owing to the subtle mode of climate variation intrinsic to the basin. Discovery of this climate phenomenon, widely known as the Indian Ocean Dipole (IOD) mode, has generated a lot of research interests in the climate community. It is shown that the IOD reduces the negative influence of El Nino on the Indian summer monsoon rainfall. However, the associated moisture divergence in the eastern Indian Ocean gives rise to a dry and warm summer over Japan through atmospheric teleconnection. The IOD influences the East African region so much so that it overwhelms the influence arising from ENSO. On the eastern side, the IOD directly influences the rainfall variations over the Maritime Continent and the ENSO through the sea level pressure variability at Darwin. Recently it is found that a “big dry” of six or more years responsible for huge economic losses and widespread forest fires (Black Saturday bushfires) in Australia was associated with the Indian Ocean phenomenon. These climate disasters have summoned a strong interest in the Indian Ocean observation and prediction.

The importance of IOD monitoring was recognized quite early in Japan and with the suggestion of Prof. Yamagata, JAMSTEC has deployed TRITON buoy in the eastern Indian Ocean in 2000. Additional deployments from USA and India have strengthened the observational network. The JAMSTEC group also developed a state of the art climate prediction model called SINTEX-F to predict IOD besides ENSO. The model has consistently predicted recent El Nino and La Nina events at least one year ahead. It has earned the highest position in the world for the ENSO predictions. However, predictability of IOD is limited by the active and chaotic intraseasonal disturbances besides prediction barriers caused by monsoon. Nevertheless, the model has predicted most of the recent IODs several seasons ahead and drawn attention of the news media and the farmers of the Asia-Pacific sector. With improvements in Indian Ocean observations and our understanding in the underlying mechanisms of high-frequency climate processes, it is expected that the climate variability in the Indian Ocean can be predicted on longer lead times.

PL-04

Towards Symbiosis between Human and Nature via Information Communication **- ‘Kurihara’ Green Project -**

(1) Norio Shiratori

President, IPSJ, Emeritus Professor, Tohoku University

(2) Kazuo Hashimoto

Tohoku University

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Industrial revolution has brought us various conveniences and boosted our economy for long. But in return we have to pay a very heavy price – the constant environmental deterioration of the very earth we are living. After much deliberation, leaders of many countries have now decided to take some concrete steps to address the issue. But this ambitious target to achieve *Green*, I think we need a symbiosis [1] between human and nature. Our tool is Information Communication. The ‘Kurihara’ Green Project is aimed to create such an environment. This is a *Ministry of Internal Affairs and Communications* project with a budget of 250 million yen for 2010. Along with Tohoku University, NTT, NTT Facilities, Hitachi and Miyagi prefecture’s Kurihara city are involved in this project and Professor Shiratori is the leader.

Our goal is to conduct a real-world experiment in the community based field to test the technical specification of necessary communication protocol, to realize network integrated control system aimed at community development to reduce environmental burden in the wide-area distributed community. Two themes have been considered, which will be achieved by the symbiosis between natural environment and human by integration of the proposed wide-area distributed community. In theme-1, wide-range cooperation-type utilization of network integration control system for symbiosis between environment and human. Theme-2 is an efficient network management system for reducing environmental burden of wide-area distributed community. Kurihara city is our experimental field, our demonstration area. There are special characteristics of Kurihara city. Human inhabitants are scattered around the entire city area including some in mountainous places. The sub-offices of this city are also far from each other. It is a perfect example of distributed system and so an ideal location to test our system.

Currently, we are observing different types of crisis around the world – political conflict, both international and regional; social problem caused by dwindling birthrate, aging population and nuclear family; environmental pollution; collapsing of long lasting social model; and the fall of capitalist market strategy. We cannot solve these crises by addressing a single problem. We have to take care considering the overall situation and their political, social and environmental aspects.

In my view, it can be done through Information technology, by harmony and symbiosis between human, technology and nature. Symbiotic computing is the factor that is missing in the present approach. Symbiotic computing combined with ecology consciousness will take us to the world we are wishing for, where elderly people will be able to live comfortable life without feeling anxious and insecure. And the children in our society can look forward to a better and Greener future. This is our concept of human-nature symbiosis.

[1] Symbiotic Computing Webpage, <http://symbiotic.agent-town.com/>

PL-05

The Good, The Bad, and The Ubiquitous

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Information ubiquity is a reality these days. Information can be accessed across the globe, at all times. Everybody, everywhere, in all spheres of life, young or old, professional or retired, is taking advantage of this ubiquity.

But this ubiquity has not been an unmixed blessing, it has brought its share of curses along. Ubiquity of information has facilitated fraud, anonymity of mischief-makers, breach of privacy of the honest citizen, and has brought danger closer home to the near and dear ones. In this session we will talk about the yet-unexplored potential and dangers of this new society with ubiquitous information, the challenges it poses and what we, in the backwaters of Tohoku, are doing about it as educators, researchers, developers and business people.

PL-06

Indo-Japan Cooperation for Agricultural Research in Semi-arid Tropics

Osamu Ito

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According to FAO agroecological zoning system, the vast area of Indian sub-continent is categorized into the semi-arid tropics (SAT), which is characterized by 75 to 180 days of length of growing period and more than 18°C of mean monthly temperature for all months. Its land has been intensively cultivated to support growing population: 48.3% of total area in India is used for agriculture, while 11.5% in Japan (FAO statistic, 2008). The contribution of agriculture to GDP in India is 17.7% against only 1.5% in Japan (UN statistics, 2008). The agriculture supports 55.4% of working population in India, while 2.5% in Japan. Although major crops grown in India are sugarcane, rice and wheat, rather favorable lands are used for those crops. Unfavorable lands, which widely spread in the SAT, if no irrigation system is established, can support only those crops which have adaptability to this environment. Sorghum, pearl millet, groundnut, pigeonpea and chickpea are widely grown in the Indian SAT. In fact, India is a world top producer of pigeonpea and third of sorghum next to USA and Nigeria. It should be a key for Indian agriculture to improve productivity of those major crops in the SAT, which will lead to stabilization of farm economy of subsistent farmers in the SAT. The SAT are characterized by two major soil types such as Alfisols and Vertisols which have tremendous potential to support regional food needs but are naturally deprived of nutrients, especially phosphorous (P) and nitrogen (N). The agricultural situation in the SAT is worsened by low and unreliable rainfall making agriculture in this environment an unpredictable enterprise. But for the 850 million people (one sixth of humanity) who inhabit this region, farming is their chief means of livelihood, a hazardous vocation on which they depend for their living. Soil fertility and water management technologies are prerequisites to increase productivity in these soils, thereby achieving food security. The Green Revolution that helped to improve crop productivity in more favorable environments of the globe has still not yet taken place in the SAT. For improvement of the crop productivity in the SAT, following points should be taken into account: 1) cereal/legume intercropping, 2) soil and water conservation and management or watershed technology, 3) crop and livestock diversification systems, 4) integration of genetic resources with natural resources management, 5) fine-tuning technologies to suit the farmers' needs and so on. The Government of Japan (GoJ) has been contributing sustainable agricultural development towards poverty alleviation and food security through the Consultative Group on International Agricultural Research (CGIAR). The Government of India has been hosting one of agricultural research institutes under CGIAR. The International Crop Research Institute for the Semi-Arid Tropics (ICRISAT) was established in Hyderabad on 1972. In addition to its core contribution to ICRISAT every year, the GoJ and ICRISAT signed in 1984 a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) to initiate a Special Project on the *Development of Sustainable Cultivation of Upland Crops in the SAT* to help improve the living conditions and household income of the smallholder farmer through research for development. During the Project, scientists developed methods to: 1) tap sources of soil P normally unavailable for plant uptake, 2) improve the N pool available to cropping systems, 3) enhance water and nutrient utilization, and 4) identify and exploit physio-genetic traits for genetic manipulation of crops that are more stable in the production environments in which they are grown. Throughout the Project period several books, and many conference papers and journal articles have been published. The Project also contributed to train Research Fellows, Visiting Scientists, and Scholars. Outline of the activities and achievements of the Project will be presented at the presentation.

PL-07

Nitrification – Is It a Strategic Point of Intervention to Limit Nitrogen Losses From Agricultural Systems? – The Concept of Biological Nitrification Inhibition (BNI) -

Guntur V Subbarao

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Human activity has had by far the single largest influence on the global N cycle as it introduces massive amounts of reactive N into the ecosystems. A major portion of this reactive N applied as fertilizer, leaks into the environment and has a cascading effect on human health; ecosystem diversity, functions and services; and global warming with negative impacts on the environment. Natural ecosystems use multiple-pathways to regulate the flow of N in the N-cycle where nitrification is suppressed and this reduces N leaks, thus they remain comparatively efficient in cycling N. In contrast, the massive amounts of N applied to the agricultural systems primarily goes through a single pathway, i.e. nitrification, an inefficient pathway that allows reactive N to leak out of the agricultural systems.

The present agricultural systems do not channel the reactive N through alternate pathways of the N cycle due to their high soil nitrifier activity, which leads to the evolution of rapidly nitrifying soil environments. Fertilizer-N consumption is expected to reach 300 Tg-y⁻¹ by 2050 from the present 150 Tg-y⁻¹. Environmental damage will result, given the pervasive inefficiencies in the use of N as <40% of the applied N is absorbed by most field crops. Asia consumes nearly 60% of the world's nitrogen fertilizer produced. It is thus desirable to develop new technologies and approaches to combat the rampant and rapid nitrification in agricultural systems.

At JIRCAS, we have developed the concept of biological nitrification inhibition (BNI) and showed that BNI is a plant function where nitrification inhibitors are released from roots that suppress soil nitrification. Sufficient evidence will be presented to demonstrate the existence, detection, regulatory mechanisms for the release of these nitrification inhibitors from plant roots. The potential for genetic enhancement for BNI capacity exists in tropical forage grasses and field crops. Future crop and pasture varieties should have a built-in genetic capacity to release nitrification inhibitors in sufficient amounts (i.e. BNI capacity) to suppress soil nitrification and to develop low-nitrifying production systems. Such agricultural production systems are critical to meet the increasing food production demands without polluting the environment with reactive nitrogen.

PL-08**Advances in Structural Metals for Society and Environment**

Kaneaki Tsuzaki

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Stronger metals are always needed to reduce weight and improve safety in transportation, enhance architectural flexibility in construction, and improve performance in heavy machinery. However, toughness and ductility decrease sharply as the strength increases. Thus, there has been a strong demand for enhanced toughness and ductility in high-strength metallic materials. This talk presents the recent activity at NIMS for advances in high strength ferrous, magnesium, and titanium alloys.

PL-09

Novel Approaches to Strengthening of Magnesium Alloys for Structural Application

Alok Singh, H. Somekawa and T. Mukai

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Magnesium is the lightest structural metal, with $1/4^{\text{th}}$ the density of steel and $2/3^{\text{rd}}$ that of aluminum. Its application to replace heavier structural alloys can result in significant reduction in the weight of automobiles, resulting in significant fuel savings and, consequently, less burden on the environment. However, magnesium alloys are known to have low strength and ductility, as compared to aluminum alloys. They also form a strong texture during processing, resulting in an anisotropy of mechanical strength. To overcome these problems and to have a dramatic increase in strength and ductility, new approaches to strengthening are required. These include control of deformation modes by changing the microstructure through processing. Another approach is application of novel phases, which exist, for example, in Mg-Zn-RE (RE=rare earth elements) alloys. One such phase is a long periodic ordered phase, which imparts very high strength but not ductility. Another is a quasicrystal phase, which enhances strength and ductility proportionately. Strength and fracture toughness in alloys containing this phase have been shown to be equal to those of aluminum alloys. A simultaneous increase of strength and ductility, not possible with intermetallic phases, is due to their special interfaces with the matrix. Recent developments in this area will be described.

POSTER SESSION

ABSTRACTS

2010

P-01

Risk Identification In Software Metrics Databases Using Graph Mining

Gufan Ahmad

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Risk identification is a crucial step in the process of software risk management and in turn, software quality assurance. It is noteworthy process for both researchers and professionals. Software metrics are key indicators to control and influence the software quality. A potential problem in software metric data may lead to profound catastrophic situation for entire software project. The current work is an endeavor to solve the risk identification problem with graph mining in smaller steps. In this simplified approach, we apply graph-mining technique in software metrics data repository to identify software risks that are associated with metric data. After thorough data visualization of graphs, the software risks are identified.

P-02**Cambodian Forest Cover monitoring for REDD Policies Implementation using Fully Polarimetric PALSAR Data**

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Forest cover monitoring has an important role for the implementation of climate change mitigation policies example Kyoto protocol and Reducing emission from deforestation and forest degradation (REDD). Various remote sensing methods are available for forest cover monitoring, but in case of tropical countries there are limitation of cloud covers. Therefore, SAR data is used in this study. Incoherent target decomposition theorems have been implemented on fully polarimetric PALSAR data to characterize the scattering of various types of forest cover. Further unsupervised and supervised classification techniques have been applied for accurately mapping of different types of forest cover. For this study, ALOS-PALSAR data have been analyzed for forest cover classification in a part of Cambodia. Finally, this information will be useful for forest cover mapping, which would eventually help in more effective implementation of REDD policies in Cambodia.

P-03**Quality of Argo Salinity Data From the Indian Ocean**Pankajakshan Thadathil^{1*}, C. C. Bajish²¹*National Institute of Oceanography, Dona Paula, Goa 403 004, India*²*Institute of Low Temperature Science, Hokkaido University, Hokkaido, Japan***Embassy of India, Tokyo (Present Address)**E-mail: ccbajish@pop.lowtem.hokudai.ac.jp*

Quality of Argo salinity data from the Indian Ocean is evaluated using ‘float-tofloat’ and ‘float-to-shipboard CTD’ match-up profiles. In both the cases, the quality evaluation has been performed at deep isotherm, where ‘potential temperature-salinity’ relation is well defined and stable. *Float-to-float* evaluation shows high level of consistency (<0.01 PSU) in salinity observation, except for initial profiles with repeat cycle numbers less than ten. For match-up pairs involving initial profiles of certain floats, salinity difference (ΔS) is found to be significantly large (> 0.01 PSU). Comparison of *float-to-float* consistency between match-up profiles from same floats and those from different floats indicates that ‘*systematic bias*’ in the float’s salinity is insignificant. Calibration of float salinity with shipboard CTD (hereinafter referred to as SCTD), at selected isotherms (3 and 7°C), shows that float-salinity is well comparable with the SCTD salinity, within a variance less than 0.01 PSU, which is the targeted accuracy of the Argo program. Specific analysis based on the age of the floats reveals that there is no significant ‘*linear drift*’ in the float’s salinity. Long-term salinity trends in water masses of the study areas are found to be insignificant to affect the estimated uncertainty/drift.

P-04

Application of Subwavelength Gratings in Liquid Crystal Displays

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A liquid crystal display (LCD) unit consists of many optical elements, such as, light source, light guide plate, polarizing, diffusing and brightness enhancing films, color filter, black matrix and finally a liquid crystal panel. One of the priorities of a modern day display engineer is to reduce the number of optical components, since; doing so would facilitate miniaturization, compactness and cost efficiency of the display unit. One way to achieve this goal is to combine various optical functions in one component. It turns out that gratings with subwavelength periods and groove depths (a few nanometers to a few hundred nanometers) can be used for this purpose. Subwavelength gratings can also be used as stand-alone elements as polarizers or optical filters. A simple grating is formed by periodically modulating the material refractive index in one direction. Typically such a grating would diffract light in multiple directions determined by the profile and period of refractive index modulation. If the period of such modulation is less than the operating wavelength, the lower-order diffracted modes would only be reflected or transmitted. We show by the help of simulation and experiments that by integrating a subwavelength dielectric or metal grating on top of the light guide plate, it is possible to polarize, collimate and homogenize the light emerging from the light-guide. Integration of grating element with the light guide helps reduce the number of individual elements. We also show using simulation how a subwavelength metal grating can be used as a polarizer or a filter. Such metal gratings allow recycling of the unused polarization component while the conventional polyvinyl acetate (PVA) based dichroic sheet polarizers do not. Also, metal gratings exhibit high polarization index and absorb less light compared to the sheet polarizers. The simulation of the metal gratings is carried out using a program implementing finite-difference time-domain (FDTD) algorithm suitable for optically dispersive materials, such as, noble metals. The program is developed in-house.

P-05

Incorporating The Concept of Zero Energy In The Newly Developed Satellite Towns of India – Case Study Rajarhat, Kolkata, India

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Indian cities have recorded an exponential growth in the last three decades in the built environment. Today 30 percent of India stays in its urban centers, expected to swell to 40 per cent by 2012¹. As cities across India are looking for solutions to this pressing problem of huge urban growth, the JNNURM, a reform-linked urban investment program of Govt. of India acts as the trigger for concentrated urban reforms and measures towards sustainable urban growth in India. In tandem with the quest of reducing the rising energy consumption, pollution and menace of climate change, the JNNURM program aims at developing the newly developed satellite towns, as Zero Energy communities. While there exists a mature body of research on the greenhouse gas contributions of individual energy-using devices such as in buildings and automobiles, there is a much less complete picture of the larger systems in which they operate, particularly urban systems. However at individual level the concepts of Zero Energy in terms of ZEH (Zero Energy Homes) or ZEB, zero net-electricity, zero net-energy has been applicable for quite some time now but harnessing them at the level of urban system interaction is still a less traversed area. This paper attempts to study the framework, methodologies and strategies of ZEST (Zero Energy Satellite Towns), built on the lines of near zero energy communities, and its applicability in the newly developed satellite town, New Town – Rajarhat, Kolkata. Firstly, it examines the individual urban factors that can be associated with lower energy use and emissions namely in built environment, urban transportation system and waste management, followed by a comprehensive inventory of integration strategies of these individual energy reduction concepts, to achieve a self sufficient – net zero energy community. A methodology is adopted to study the land use and transport network to analyze the existing situation of Rajarhat and possibility of converting it to a ZEST. Model uses the present data of Rajarhat along with the future projected data as per the Concept Plan, New Town, Rajarhat². Finally a spatial solution and policy framework is envisaged to promote low carbon and energy efficient society.

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P-06

Unusual Thermal Stability on Parallel Duplex Upon LNA Modification

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The vast usage of oligonucleotides as biological sensors and therapeutic tools faces limitation due to the instability of the nucleic acids in biological fluids and moderate affinity towards complementary strands. Chemically synthesized modified nucleic acids with high thermal stability and hybridization efficiency can be a potential solution to these problems. In this study we report the formation and stabilization mechanism of a stable duplex influenced by locked nucleic acid (LNA) modifications under physiological conditions. The parallel stranded duplex of PuP (5'-AGAAAGAGAAGA-3') and Py0 (5'-TCTTTCTCTTCT-3') at pH 5.0 was converted to anti-parallel duplex with two bulges at pH 7.0. When the cytosine bases of Py0 stand were fully modified with LNA, it formed parallel duplex even at physiological pH with very high thermal stability.

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P-07**Use of Agro-Residual Extract for Enhanced Production of Xylanase by
Melanocarpus albomyces Mutant**

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The wild type filamentous fungus, *Melanocarpus albomyces*, produces many commercially valuable enzymes like xylanases along with xylan-debranching enzymes with low activity. For the first time, the mutants of *M. albomyces* were developed from vegetative spores. Profuse sporulation of *M. albomyces* was induced on Potato Carrot Agar medium. These spores when subjected to chemical mutation led to the isolation of hyper-xylanase producing mutant, viz, *M. albomyces* IITD3A. Various parameters like number of spores, nitrogen source and C/N ratio of the medium were optimized for production of xylanase by the mutant in shake flask. Further, on statistical optimization of the process parameters by response surface methodology revealed that the production of xylanase was most affected by changes in the pH of the production medium which contained a soluble extract of wheat straw as the sole carbon source. When the pH of the production medium in 14 L bioreactor was controlled on-line at 7.8, xylanase activity of 415 IU.ml⁻¹ was obtained after 36 h fermentation. On cycling the pH between 7.8 and 8.2, the same activity could be attained in 24 h with overall productivity of 16,670 IU.L⁻¹h⁻¹, which was 12-fold higher than the value obtained with the wild type culture on insoluble wheat straw. The xylanase at pH 7.5 and temperature 55°C retained 100% of its original activity. Even at pH 9.0 it retained more than 50% of its activity for 2 h, which is promising for application in Pulp and paper industry.

P-08

Role of Peptidylarginine Deiminase 4 (PAD4) In Mammalian Preimplantation Embryonic Development

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Peptidylarginine deiminases are a family of calcium dependent, highly substrate specific enzymes that convert peptide bound arginine residues into non conventional amino acid citrulline in a post translational modification known as citrullination. Among the known 5 isomers, peptidylarginine deiminase 4 (PAD4) having nuclear localizing sequence, is localized in the nucleus and is known to target histones and nucleophosmin. It has been shown that modifications mediated by PAD4 are involved in regulating chromatin structure and gene expression in a variety of cell types. Here we study the localization and expression of PAD4 in pig (*sus scrofa*) oocytes and electrically activated embryos and analyze its role in the preimplantation embryonic development. 4-6 mm sized follicles were extracted from the ovaries collected from the local slaughter house and cultured for maturation in vitro. Oocytes were collected at different stages of maturation for analysis. Fully matured metaphase oocytes with extruded 1st polar body collected at 42-46 hrs post maturation culture were electrically stimulated. Thus activated embryos were collected at different developmental stages for the investigation. Indirect immunofluorescence assays and western blot analyses, showed that PAD4 is primarily localized in the cytosol in all the stages of oocytes and embryos. However, in germinal vesicle oocyte, PAD4 was also found to have translocated into the nucleus before germinal vesicle break down and there upon colocalized with the metaphase spindle. Again at the blastocyst stage PAD4 was found to have translocated into the nuclei. PAD4 substrate specificity was dissected using modified citrulline detection kit and it was discovered that histone H3 was the target of peptidylarginine deiminase 4 in oocytes and embryos. When PAD4 expression was knocked down via RNA interference, it was observed that there was delay in the development, which lead to retarded growth. The delay was noticed at each developmental stage. There was significant decrease in the blastocyst cell number. When PAD4 expression and localization was also checked in mouse oocytes and parthenogenetic embryos, metaphase oocytes showed similar PAD4 localization pattern and the PAD4 expression was seen in all the stages of embryos too. To check whether somatic cells also contain PAD4, cumulus cells collected during denudation of metaphase oocytes were examined for the presence of PAD4 as well as citrullinated proteins in the nucleus by both indirect immunofluorescence and western blotting analyses. It was revealed that PAD4 was predominantly cytoplasmic and histone H3, H2 and H4 were the targets. Thus our study confirms the presence of PAD4 in the pig oocytes, embryos and cumulus cells; PAD4 nuclear translocation in the later stages of oocyte development and during fertilization; and leads to the conclusion that PAD4 is involved in the development of pig pre-implantation embryos.

P-09**Analysis of Scattered Radio Signal From Chipless RFID Using Stacked
Multilayer Patches**Kyohei Chiba, Goutam Chakraborty

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Application of RFID for information dissemination is getting increasingly popular. The main drawback of the existing technology is cost, and in case of passive RFID the proximity needed to be able to read it. Recently, multilayer metallic patches are proposed to be used as RFID. Analyzing the scattered chirp signal, it is possible to find the RFID's (in fact, the patch antenna's) parameters, which are but the information embedded in the patch. Due to non-linear transfer function, and presence of noise, the task is non-trivial. In this work, we propose soft-computing techniques to solve this problem.

P-10**Long-Term (1900-2009) Observed Warming Over Japan:
An Assessment of Urban Influence**

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The present study considers the total amount of surface warming over Japan through analyzing the annual mean surface air temperature of 60 reliable synoptic stations that have records of 1870s onwards. The spatial pattern of up-to-date (1900-2009) observed warming over Japan depends significantly on size of population rather on latitude/longitude, indicates the existence of urban contamination in the long term trend. The urban contamination is extensively estimated selecting three sets of rural stations (17_JMA, 13_OUR and 12_SAT) using JMA recommended rural sites, meta-data information (mean city population) and satellite imagery, respectively. The trends of 53 out of 60 (89%) stations reported here have trend-to-noise ratios greater than 1.96 and regarded as statistically significant at 95% level. The regionally averaged mean annual temperature within Japan has increased by 1.75°C (noticeably higher than other countries); the surrounding oceans (25 – 50°N and 120 - 150°E) have warmed by 0.96°C in the last 11-decades during the period of 1900-2009. The 9 highly populated cities (Sapporo, Tokyo, Yokohama, Kyoto, Osaka, Nagoya, Hiroshima, Kobe, and Fukuoka) show an warming trend of 2.40°C in the same period. The urban contamination (urban - rural warming) in the long-term trend was estimated to 0.10°C/decade and 0.04°C/decade due to metropolitan and suburb cities, respectively. All sets of Japanese rural stations showed relatively higher warming exhibits natural variability and indicate the existence of urban bias therein. Therefore, urban bias in the three sets of rural stations was also estimated using the land/sea warming trends of 19 CMIP3 climate model experiments for the 20C3M simulations in which urbanization effect were not represented and assumed to be reproduced the “real rural warming” but not the actual warming observed in all-Japan station data. The time series of annual mean temperature of 60 Japanese stations data has been affected by urbanization of 0.51°C considering the model predicted rural warming of 0.90°C in the last century (900-1999).

P-11**Assessing The Performance of The IPCC Climate Models Across Generations Over Eastern India**

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In this study we investigate the performance of models from the Intergovernmental Panel for Climate Change (IPCC) assessment reports on the scale of the Gangetic West Bengal region of east India ($6^{\circ}\times 6^{\circ}$). Analysing present-day seasonal rainfall and temperature over the domain, we compare the results from the models from the six modelling centres common to the second, third and fourth assessment reports (abbreviated to SAR, TAR and AR4 respectively) in order to judge to what extent these global models have improved on the regional scale. Metrics for model evaluation are not yet firmly established in the literature, so in this paper we compare and contrast the results from a number of different statistics used in previous studies. We also analyse the impact of topography on the results obtained for the AR4 models.

We find that most models improved from SAR to AR4, although there is some variation in this result depending on seasons, variables and on which statistical methods are used in the analysis. The multi-model mean of the six models improves from SAR to TAR to AR4. The overall best performance on this regional scale in the AR4 is the Japanese model, MIROC, but the best model in terms of improving skill from SAR to AR4 is the GFDL model from the United States. Correcting for errors in the model topographies produced an overall improvement of spatial patterns and error statistics, and greatly improves the performance of one model (CGCM), which has poor topography, but does not affect the ranking of the other models.

P-12

Mortalin Staining as A Reporter Tool For Anti-Cancer Drug Screening

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Mortalin is a member of the hsp70 family of proteins and shows differential cellular distribution in human normal and cancer cells; pancytoplasmic in normal and perinuclear in cancer cells. Induction of senescence in cancer cells by a variety of chemicals and stress conditions resulted in the shift of staining pattern from the perinuclear to pancytoplasmic type along with the nuclear translocation and activation of p53 function. We provide evidence that mortalin staining can be used for drug screening for cancer therapy. In this study, we used mortalin staining as a model reporter and screened human shRNA library for candidate anticancer siRNAs. By four rounds of screening, we identified siRNAs that caused shift in mortalin staining from the perinuclear to the pancytoplasmic pattern. The role of selected gene targets in cancer was validated by (i) genomic analysis through comparative genomic hybridization, (ii) gene specific genomic PCR analyses, (iii) impact on p53 and p16 activities, and (iv) pathway analyses by bioinformatics approach. We report DNA damage signaling pathway as a candidate target for cancer therapy.

P-13

Microwave Assisted Synthesis of Biologically Active Heterocycles

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Microwave-assisted organic synthesis is a rapidly growing field in organic chemistry.¹ In the early days, domestic microwaves were used with poor reproducibility. Moreover, accidents were common due to the lack of control. The recent introduction of specifically designed and constructed microwave equipment by CEM, Milestone, Biotage, Plazmatronika, Anton Paar, Shikoku Instrumentation, EYELA and so on allowing for the on-line monitoring of temperature, power, pressure, countering safety, and reproducibility concerns has led to widespread use of microwaves in synthetic organic chemistry. On the other hand, making reaction times shorter and expanding the reaction range offered by microwave assisted organic synthesis are suited to the increased demands of industry. In particular the pharmaceutical industry requires the production of a higher number of novel chemical entities, which requires chemists to employ a number of resources to reduce the time for the production of compounds.

Synthesis of biologically active heterocycles with carbohydrate mimetic is gaining interest in recent years. Carbohydrate modification to heterocycles can bring several advantages to be useful new drugs, as increasing solubility in water, transportation to particular part to where the modified oligosaccharide can bind, reducing toxicity, and so on.

This presentation will discuss synthesis of novel biologically active heterocyclic libraries like oxadiazoles,² isoxazolines,³ isoxazoles etc. and some sugar mimic via cycloaddition reactions by microwave irradiation. A new library of diclofenac sugar hydrazones and their oxadiazoline derivatives were synthesized by microwave heating. It will also discuss microwave assisted synthesis of the anti-hyperglycemic drug rosiglitazone.⁴ The advantages of microwave irradiation over conventional heating are shorter reaction time, selectivity, increased yield and quality.

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P-14**Synthesis, luminescence, field-emission properties and prospects N-Doped ZnO Nanobullets**

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Crystallization in solution, in the absence of external influences, is expected to lead to growth that is symmetric at least in two opposite facets. Such was not the case when ZnO nanostructures were synthesized solvothermally. The reaction product was rather found to consist of tiny bullet-shaped single crystals with abrupt hexagonal bases and sharp tips. A careful analysis revealed that one of the reaction intermediates with sheet-like morphology acts as a self-sacrificing template and induces such unexpected and novel growth. The synthesis was further extended to dope the nanobullets with nitrogen as previous studies showed this can induce p-type behavior in ZnO, which is complementary to the naturally occurring n-type ZnO. Herein, a soft-chemical approach is used for the first time for this purpose, which is otherwise accomplished only with high-temperature techniques. Investigations using cathodoluminescence (CL) spectroscopy reveal stable optical behavior within a pure nanobullet, while the CL spectra from the surfaces and the cores of the doped samples are different, pointing at a N-rich core. Even though N-doped ZnO is known to have high conductivity, our study demonstrates that the field-emission characteristics of ZnO can also be enhanced by means of N doping.

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A Collaborative Computational Platform for Curation and Enrichment of Biological Pathways

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Current biological research is heavily dependent on information technology and computational resources – from literature databases, genomic and pathway databases, to a whole array of web-based information resources. Nevertheless, current modes of information storage, retrieval and sharing suffer from fragmented and non-standardized formats, isolated tools with little inter-tool communications, forcing researchers to use disparate tools and databases affecting their research workflows and productivity. This is particularly true for the curation of large scale biological pathway maps, which require genome-wide system-oriented research collecting fine-grained information of molecular interactions and gene regulations in an up-to-date manner for reconstruction and visual representation.

Towards this direction, we present a novel open-flow paradigm for pathway curation and enrichment, which envisions providing an integrated suite of standards and tools to automate the pathway curation workflow. We present the pathway curation workflow, together with a suite of software modules developed around the pathway editor CellDesigner™, to implement the workflow elements, **Collect** – retrieve information from various pathway databases (Panther, BioModels) as well custom spreadsheet data formats; **Curate** – construction of pathways on CellDesigner™ (www.celldesigner.org), together with tools to *mine* literature from text-mining engines and *merge* pathways components; **Annotate** – support for custom annotations, MIRIAM based annotations as well genomic databases like iHOP and Entrez; **Share** - open, community-based enrichment through support for sharing pathways on web-based curation platform, *Payao* (www.payaologue.org), as well as various other media. The workflow is based on open standards of SBML and SBGN, thereby allowing researchers to re-use workflow on other standard compliant platforms.

We demonstrate the successful application of the open flow curation paradigm in a joint collaboration between Council of Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR) Open Source Drug Discovery (OSDD) initiative in India (www.osdd.net) for creating a large scale metabolic map of the pathogenic bacteria *Mycobacterium Tuberculosis (Mtb)*, involving hundreds of students and researchers working in an open collaborative manner for re-annotating the Mtb genome.

P-16

Photoswitching of Benzene Rotor And Induction of Molecular Chirality By Circular Polarized Light In Cyclic Azobenzenophane

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Induction of molecular chirality by physical or chemical methods and its amplification in molecules or its assemblies have been attracted the interest of chemists for long time, particularly in connection with the homo-chiral structures in nature. The various physical factors so far used include mechanical stirring, introduction of chiral environment in the form of chiral solvents or chiral additives. Importantly the chiral nature of light also has been used for this purpose. The light induced chirality in molecules has obtained greater attention since the chirality of the light is believed to be one of the reasons for the origin of homo-chiral structures observed in nature. Our group was particularly interested for design and synthesis of azobenzene molecular devices. Recently for the first time we reported light controlled complete ON-OFF rotation of naphthalene rotor in cyclic azobenzenophanes¹. Here we demonstrate a new class of photo-driven molecular brake and its application as chiral sensors for the induction of molecular chirality by circularly polarized light (CPL).

In the present study, we describe design and synthesis of a light controlled molecular machine based on azobenzenophane consisting of (2,5-dimethoxy, dimethyl or difluoro-) 1,4-dioxybenzene rotating unit and dioxyazobenzene photoisomerizable moiety bridged together by a fixed bismethylene spacer. Depends upon substitution on benzene rotor this system shows conformational restriction on the free rotation of the benzene moiety, thereby imparting the molecule with planar chirality. The compound with 2,5-dimethylbenzene as rotor was demonstrated as light controlled molecular brake; wherein free rotation of rotor is completely stopped in *trans* isomer while the rotation is allowed in the *cis* isomer. NMR, HPLC and CD spectroscopy confirmed the property of compound as molecular brake. In the case of dimethoxy-benzene as rotor, brake ON and for difluorobenzene rotor brake OFF were observed both in *trans* and *cis* isomers. So by appropriate selection of substituent on benzene moiety or by photoirradiation we could control the rotation of benzene rotor in cyclic azobenzenophanes and this type of molecular level control is useful for the development of artificial molecular machines. Nevertheless, by utilizing the stability of the chiral structure in *trans*, fast racemization in *cis* and the circular dichroism in the photoisomerizable *trans* isomer, partial enrichment of (S)-or (R)-enantiomers upon exposure to *r*-or *l*- circular polarized light at 488 nm was demonstrated. We expect this type of simple cyclic azobenzenophane can represent a model compound, which may explain the asymmetric imbalance of the molecule in the nature, with a new photo-resolution path, i.e. the ground state chirality induction of one of the enantiomer from a racemizing *cis* isomer.

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P-17**Relationship Between The Iron And Primary Production In The Ocean**

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The aim of this study is to explore the relationship between the iron and phytoplankton using an ocean circulation and ecosystem model. The Sun is the source of energy for most of the living things on the Earth. But, it is only the green living things such as plants that can directly utilize the sun energy. In the ocean, phytoplankton is the green living things. Phytoplankton is starting point for food chain in the ocean because it contains photosynthetic pigments mainly Chlorophyll-a, and produces organic matter from inorganic matter by photosynthesis by utilizing light and nutrients. The Nutrients can be divided in to two groups, macro- and micronutrients. Based on the nutrient availability, the ocean system can be divided into coastal region and open ocean region. In the coastal region, high productivity is a typical feature because macronutrients are supplied from rivers. However, in the open ocean, macronutrients are provided by upwelling and mixing from deep water while micro-nutrients are mainly supplied through the atmosphere. Generally, productivity in the coastal region is higher than that of the open ocean. The iron (Fe), one of the micronutrients, is considered to be an essential element for phytoplankton, because it affects on an enzyme when phytoplankton synthesizes the organic matter. Considering the importance of Fe, some regions of the World Ocean are identified as HNLC (High Nutrients Low Chlorophyll) regions. In the HNLC regions, although the macronutrients are abundant, chlorophyll concentrations are lower than the expected level. This can be attributed to paucity of Fe. Moreover, Fe also affects the climate, because the difference in the iron fluxes can cause variability in the distribution of phytoplankton and as a result in the absorption of CO₂ by export fluxes. Furthermore, phytoplankton is also considered to influence the climate as it releases DMS (dimethyl sulfide) to the atmosphere, which can eventually act as nuclei of the cloud that could potentially block solar radiation from reaching the ocean surface. Against this background, we undertake this study to understand the relationship between the iron and phytoplankton by using the numerical model. We attempt to investigate the relevant issues by using the ocean ecosystem model, which incorporates the explicit iron cycle into the model.

P-18

Localization of Chemotaxis-Related Components of System I & III of *Vibrio cholerae* Under Aerobic And Anaerobic Conditions

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Vibrio cholerae, the etiological agent of cholera disease, is a highly motile bacterium with a single polar flagellum. Chemotaxis is best studied with *E. coli*. Central to the chemotactic signal transduction is a phosphate relay from the histidine kinase CheA and the response regulator CheY, which constitute a two-component regulatory system. CheA is activated when coupled to an unliganded chemoreceptor along with adaptor protein CheW, which phosphorylates itself and then transfers the phosphate group to CheY. Binding of phospho-CheY to the switch complex of the flagellar motor induces its clockwise (CW), which otherwise would be counterclockwise (CCW) rotation, resulting in reorientation of the cell. The chemoreceptors, which are homodimeric transmembrane proteins, localize at a cell pole and form a huge hexagonal array with a trimer of dimers as a building unit. CheW and CheA, as well as other Che proteins, target to the receptor cluster to form an exquisite signaling supramolecular complex or signalosome. Receptor clustering is shown to be critical for signal amplification and adaptation.

The genome sequence of *V. cholerae* has revealed that it possesses three sets of proteins with similarity to conventional chemotaxis-signaling proteins (Che proteins). Each set constitutes a distinct system, but only System II is directly involved in chemotaxis.

To get an insight into the functions of the other systems, we examined the sub-cellular localization of the histidine kinases (CheA1 and CheA3) and adaptor proteins (putCheW, CheW2 and CheW3) of System I and System III by using GFP fusions and found that all these proteins localized to a pole when incubated without shaking, but their polar localization was lost after vigorous shaking. Shaking with N₂ allowed polar localization of CheA1. Furthermore, the polar localization of CheA1 and CheA3 was induced by the addition of sodium azide or carbonyl cyanide *m*-chlorophenylhydrazone (CCCP) under aerobic conditions. These results suggest that polar localization of the System I and III components are controlled in response to changes in energy metabolism.

The fact that the formation of the receptor-kinase supramolecular complexes is triggered by anaerobic conditions raises the possibility that these systems function in specific environments such as human intestine. A more detailed study of Systems I and III are essential to elucidate the precise roles of these systems in different environments and to further our understanding in survival and pathogenicity of *V. cholerae*.

P-19

Inhibitory Mechanisms of 3-(4-Hydroxyphenyl) Propionate (MHPP) And Sakuranetin, The Biological Nitrification Inhibitors Released From Sorghum Roots, On *Nitrosomonas*

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The ability to suppress soil nitrification by releasing inhibitors from roots, a plant function termed 'biological nitrification inhibition' (BNI). Among major food crops, sorghum showed significant BNI-capacity. *Nitrosomonas*, the nitrifying bacteria, oxidizes ammonia into nitrite in two enzymatic steps. Ammonia is first oxidized to hydroxylamine by ammonia monooxygenase (AMO), a membrane-bound enzyme; hydroxylamine is then oxidized to nitrite by hydroxylamine oxidoreductase (HAO), a periplasmic enzyme. The objective of this study is to analyze the mode of inhibition from MHPP and sakuranetin, the nitrification inhibitors released from sorghum roots. An assay using recombinant luminescent *Nitrosomonas europaea* is adopted to detect inhibitory activity in plant-root systems. MHPP and sakuranetin showed a differential mode of inhibitory action. Sakuranetin at ≤ 10 mM inhibited *Nitrosomonas* by blocking only the AMO pathway, but at 100 mM, blocked both AMO and HAO pathways. Irrespective of the concentration (≥ 100 mM in assay), MHPP blocked only the AMO pathway. Double-reciprocal plot analysis (Lineweaver-Burk plot) showed that MHPP inhibited *Nitrosomonas* un-competitively, indicating that its AMO binding site is different from that of ammonia. We hypothesize that MHPP forms a complex with AMO enzyme, thereby preventing it to oxidize ammonia. All three synthetic nitrification inhibitors (allylthiourea, nitrapyrin and dicyandiamide) inhibited *Nitrosomonas* by blocking only the AMO pathway irrespective of their concentrations in assay (≥ 1000 mM). Crude methanol extracts of sorghum root exudates containing BNI-activity inhibited *Nitrosomonas* by blocking both AMO and HAO enzymatic pathways. The multi-mode of inhibitory action from these BNIs released from sorghum roots may contribute to the stability of the inhibitory function on nitrifying bacteria, thus could provide effective control on soil nitrification in sorghum production systems.

P-20**Reconstitution And Verification of Hypothetical Signal Transduction Cascade of *Arabidopsis* Stomatal Developmental Pathway**

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Stomata regulate gas and water vapour exchange between plant and their environment. Secretory peptides EPF1 and EPF2 negatively regulate stomata developmental pathway. The actions of EPF1 and EPF2 require the *TMM* receptor like protein and the ER-family receptor kinases. *STOMAGEN* positively regulates stomatal density and belongs to the *EPF1* and *EPF2* family. Disruption of genes for *TMM*, the ER-family receptor kinases, or MAPK cascade components results in excess formation of stomata without proper placement. The MAPK cascade targets the bHLH class transcription factor SPCH, which is required for entry into the stomatal lineage. Taken all genetic evidences in consideration, we can generate a model in which the extracellular signaling peptides EPF1 and EPF2 are perceived by putative receptor complexes that contain *TMM* and ER family protein, which in turn activates the MAPK cascade, phosphorylate SPCH, and inhibit stomatal formation. However, the action of secretory peptides was not proven directly. Therefore, we are trying to reconstitute the whole components by transient expression in tobacco leaves, and verify the above model. Here we show that overexpression of EPF1 and EPF2 decreased SPCH-GFP protein level. *STOMAGEN*, on the other hand increased the SPCH-GFP protein. Our study also provided evidence that the action of EPF1 and EPF2 on SPCH-GFP level depends on MAPK cascade. Our results support the above model.

REDEFINE: A GPP-Reconfigurable Architecture Hybrid

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General Purpose Processors (GPPs) typically contain a linear array of functional units interconnected through a bypass channel, which enables exchange of data. However, the bypass channel is area and power inefficient. Replacing this interconnect with a lower degree interconnect provides an opportunity to reduce the power and area overheads. Further the compute elements are arranged in a planar fashion and communications are made explicit as in Transport Triggered Architectures. Such architecture provides a scalable solution to increasing the number of functional units. The planar arrangement of compute elements reduces the total available memory bandwidth since it scales by the semi-perimeter while the number of compute elements scales quadratically. This requires special schemes to overlap the instruction execution time with the instruction launch of the next configuration. We introduce the notion of branch prediction and use a static branch predictor to speculative prefetch the subsequent configuration to be executed. The planar arrangement of compute elements allows us to perform spatial computation, alongside the temporal computation already present in GPPs. The spatio-temporal nature of computation necessitates newer compilation methodologies for exploiting the spatial nature of the computation fabric. The compiler divides the application's control flow graph into subgraphs called HyperOp. Each HyperOp executes using *strict function semantics* on the CE fabric. To enable execution the HyperOps need to be partitioned and assigned to individual CEs. We explore a unique partitioning schemes based on Edge Centrality to perform efficient partitioning of the HyperOp Graphs. This interesting hybrid between GPP and Reconfigurable Architectures helps exploit this processor as a standalone processor or a co-processor.

P-22

Bio-Inspired Artificial Peptides Incorporating Novel Non-Biological Chromophores With Designed Functionalities For Device Applications

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Biomolecular materials comprising of *de novo* designed amphiphilic 4-helix bundle peptides incorporating novel non-biological functional chromophores have been developed for charge separation and non-linear optical applications, based on bio-inspiration approach. Hierarchical organization of these nanoscale peptide-chromophore complexes into ordered 2-D and 3-D assemblies, by means of Langmuir-Schaefer and molecular self-assembly techniques ensure the conversion of their microscopic molecular properties into macroscopic material properties of the ensemble. Structural studies performed on monolayer ensembles of these complexes at air-water interface, using optical spectroscopy, grazing incidence x-ray diffraction (GIXD) and x-ray reflectivity (XR), indicate that these amphiphilic peptides specifically bind and orient the non-biological chromophores containing extended conjugated metalloporphyrins. Binding specificity is achieved via axial histidyl ligation of the metalloporphyrin moiety in the cofactor, while vectorial orientation of the complexes derives from the strong amphiphilicity of the peptide bundle. Transfer of these monolayer ensembles on to solid substrates leads to the formation of hierarchical functional materials that have the potential for device applications.

As an example, a novel "push-pull" chromophore (**RuPZn**) based on extended π -electron systems has been designed to exhibit exceptionally large molecular hyperpolarizabilities. In addition, we have engineered an amphiphilic 4-helix bundle peptide (**AP0**) to vectorially incorporate the hyperpolarizable chromophore having a zinc porphyrin moiety, with high specificity into the interior core of the bundle. The amphiphilic exterior of the bundle facilitates the formation of densely-packed monolayer ensembles of vectorially oriented **AP0-RuPZn** complexes at the air-water interface. Chemical specificity designed into the ends of the bundle facilitates the subsequent covalent attachment of these monolayer ensembles onto the surface of an inorganic substrate. Structural characterization of these monolayer ensembles at each stage of their fabrication starting from the precursor to the final material will be presented in addition to the second harmonic generation (SHG) studies illustrating the usability of these materials for non-linear optical (NLO) device applications.

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P-23**A homologue of mitochondrial translocator subunit TIM50 modulates endoreduplication in darkness**

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Endoreduplication is a kind of cell cycle that increases nuclear DNA content (ploidy) without cell and nuclear division and is important for plant development. Here we screened mutants showing increased polyploidy from RIKEN *Arabidopsis* full length cDNA Overexpressor lines (FOX lines) and found that one of the FOX line F07144 showed increase in polyploidy in darkness and the corresponding gene encoded a homologue of mitochondrial translocator subunit TIM50. Tim50 maintains the permeability barrier of mitochondria by closing the translocation pore in presequence regulated manner. We checked sub-cellular localization of expressed protein in F07144 line using GFP markers and found that this protein was localized in mitochondria, so this F07144 protein can be designated as *AtTIM50*. GFP fused *AtTim50* degrades very rapidly and this degradation were stabilized by MG132, a proteasome inhibitor. Additionally loss of function mutant (SALK_059376) showed decrease in polyploidy and reduced plant growth and also showed low ATP levels than that of wild type plants. Histochemical analysis using GUS reporter gene system showed expression pattern almost everywhere like cotyledons, root hairs and hypocotyls but abundantly concentrated in highly endoreduplicating cells. Here, we demonstrate that *AtTIM50* regulate endoreduplication through cellular ATP-levels.

Controlled Orientation of One-Dimensional Mesochannel Alignments in Mesoporous Silica Films Using Lyotropic Liquid Crystals

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Among the various surfactant templated mesoporous materials, transparent thin films, in particular two dimensional (2D) hexagonal mesoporous films have been paid much attention due to their promising applications in various fields. Fine controls of 1D mesochannels in a certain direction is much required in order to employ these materials as the recording media, nanofluidic, optoelectronic devices, and fabrication of the oriented nanowires. External fields such as electric and magnetic fields, shear flows have been utilised as well know alignment strategies for the controlled alignment. However these methods need special requirements on the supported substrate using lithographic techniques and oriented polymer films. Most of the alignment works have been carried out using either ionic surfactants (CTAB) or non-ionic surfactant with (Brij 56) with pore size limited to less than 3 nm, which is unfavourable towards many applications. Although mesoporous silica films with large mesochannels are reported by dip-coating method, definite evidence of alignments and precise controlled alignment were not presented. Herein, we demonstrate a facile method for the controlled orientation of 1D mesochannels utilising lyotropic liquid crystals (LLC) based precursors uniformly coated on the substrates by novel rubbing method. This method doesn't need any special requirements on the supports of the substrate. We applied this rubbing method for the uniaxial orientation of mesochannels in mesoporous silica films using different surfactants such as P123 and Brij 56. This advantageous method provides strict control of uniaxial orientation of mesochannels without any disorder, tuning the mesopore size over a wide range and multi-layered mesoporous thin films with different orientations can also be achieved.

In the both cases of P123 and Brij 56 systems, the conventional θ -2 θ XRD of the as-prepared films showed strong diffraction peaks correspond to (10) and (20) diffractions of the 2D-hexagonal structure which is also confirmed by the diffraction spots from GI-SAXS measurements. The cross-sectional TEM images of the as-prepared films confirmed that the mesochannels are running parallel throughout to the substrate. Even at the interface between the films and the substrate surfaces, the 1D mesochannels of continuous hexagonal mesostructure were successfully oriented parallel along the rubbing direction. We measured the change of intensities during the rotation (α) and observed two peaks every 180° and it is considered that almost all mesochannels in the film are uniaxially oriented along the rubbing direction. The accessible mesoporosity was confirmed from the nitrogen adsorption/desorption measurements. We consider that the orientation of the 1D mesochannels was induced by the strong rubbing motion. The precursor solution before the rubbing shows liquid crystals with highly concentrated surfactants. The rubbing and its direction itself leads to the rapid motion of the precursor solution in a uniaxial direction on the substrate. Then, the tubular-shaped micelles are anisotropically arranged along the rubbing direction. Furthermore, we can produce multilayer film with the different orientations of mesochannels in different layers by simply controlling the rubbing direction. In order to prepare such a film, the precursor solutions were placed once again on the top of the film and rubbed perpendicularly to the first layer film.

P-25**Response of Phytoplankton Functional Groups to 1997-98 Indian Ocean Dipole (IOD) in the Eastern Tropical Indian Ocean**Kedarnath Mahapatra¹, Yoshihiro Okada²¹*Earth Weather Inc./ Institute of Oceanic Research & Development/ Social Partnership Innovation Center, Tokai University, 3-20-1 Orido, Shimizu-ku, Shizuoka 424-8610, Japan*²*School of Marine Science and Technology, Tokai University**3-20-1 Orido, Shimizu-ku, Shizuoka 424-8610, Japan**E-mail: kedar@scc.u-tokai.ac.jp*

Our understanding of the influence of atmospheric and oceanic forcing conditions associated with the Indian Ocean Dipole (IOD) on ecosystem dynamics and biogeochemical processes of the eastern tropical Indian Ocean (ETIO) is limited due to lack of long-term observational data on the chemical and biological oceanographic variables. In the present study, we used monthly nutrient (nitrate) and chlorophyll data representing 4 phytoplankton functional groups (PFGs) i.e. diatoms, chlorophytes (represents prasinophytes, pelagophytes, and other nanoflagellates), cyanobacteria (represents all picoprokaryotes), and coccolithophores as derived from the NASA Ocean Biogeochemical Model (NOBM), a coupled three-dimensional circulation/biogeochemical/radiative model to understand interaction of biological processes with the anomalous physical and chemical processes associated with the IOD cycle. Successful assimilation of satellite derived chlorophyll data in the NOBM provided the first glimpse of the evolution of phytoplankton ecosystem dynamics during the IOD event of 1997-98 in the ETIO. Three phases of the IOD cycle viz. peaking, decaying and reversal were well captured in the evolution of ecosystem dynamics in the ETIO and the surrounding waters. Each phase was found to characterize a specific biogeochemical set up that facilitated the PFGs to thrive and cross-dominate each other in the ETIO. The dramatic ecosystem perturbations associated with the 1997-98 IOD would not have been explained physically and biogeochemically had it not been for the NOBM that simulates distribution of important ecological and geochemical components in the oceans in a multi-phytoplankton context using circulation and turbulence dynamics, irradiance availability, and the interaction among different phytoplankton groups. Development and validation of biogeochemical models will be necessary to elucidate further the processes that drive the biogeochemical fluctuations in this region. For that, moorings equipped with sensors for biological and chemical variables should be included in future equatorial Indian Ocean observation programs. Further research is also needed on physiological and phenological aspects of PFGs to understand the intensity of response of the pelagic assemblages to the climatological changes as well as its potential impact on annually recurring cycle of pelagic trophodynamics and ecosystem functions.

P-26**Functional Genomics Resource Development In Wheat**

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Wheat is an important food crop. Due to its polyploidy nature (16 Gb, AABBDD), the progress in genomics studies are in slower phase when compared to smaller genomes like rice (430 Mb) and arabidopsis (120 Mb). To address this issue, we are developing functional genomics resources for wheat to carry out future research.

Linkage mapping and QTL identification is pre-requisite for map-based cloning of any gene of interest and marker assisted selection. We have developed the first SSR linkage map for Chinese Spring/Spelt recombinant inbred lines and identified QTLs for spike related and β -glucan traits (Manickavelu et al. 2010).

Development of ESTs has been recognized as a rapid method of sampling an organism's transcriptome. In the large and repetitive genome of bread wheat, the transcriptome approach is complementary to a whole genome sequencing project. We have initiated a wheat EST project in Japan and constructed around 55 cDNA libraries (~0.9 million) from various tissues and strains of wheat including many treatments. EST assembly and SNP mining was carried out. Among the libraries, two were selected and the gene expression pattern after leaf rust infection was compared in near-isogenic wheat lines differed for *Lr10* leaf rust resistance gene (Manickavelu et al. 2010).

For reverse genetic studies, mutant lines were developed and currently searching for new alternative green revolution genes.

P-27**TERI: Introduction on Its Sustainable And Biomass Energy Activities**

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In order to address the global issues pertaining to the climate change, rapid depletion of the natural resources and environmental degradation on account of the use of fossil fuels, The Energy and Resources Institute (TERI) provides clean and cost-effective solutions to energy needs of diverse user-groups. The main focus of TERI is on activities based on promoting renewable energy and to make the applications and user area more sustainable by itself. The broad spectrum of its activities mainly under renewable energy ranges from project development to developing and addressing policies, planning and regulatory aspects etc in order to promote the green concepts in the urban settings. Whereas, at rural areas, under biomass energy, the main activities ranges from biomass-gasifier based energy to remote rural communities to facilitate renewables based large-scale power generation; along with efficient utilization of biomass in small and micro-enterprises to enhancing resource efficiency in a variety of industrial applications. The different products are developed and used under biomass energy i.e., biomass gasifiers for heating and power generation applications, high efficiency cook-stoves and pyrolyzers for bio-oil production. These activities are mainly for providing the base for the growth of the sustainable energy utilization.

The global presence and reach attained by TERI thus provides a platform for the future associations with other institutes or organizations of same interests, who plans to have joint renewable energy based projects or joint development and dissemination of renewable energy based technologies for the betterment of the rural lives and for increasing the energy efficiency at urban sectors, in and outside India.

P-28**Estimation of Zooplankton Biomass in Deep Sea Using New Ocean Carbon Circulation Model with Additional Plankton Functional Groups**

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Absorption of carbon dioxide (CO₂) from air to sea-surface is influenced by phytoplankton. Phytoplankton, which is known as primary producers, uses CO₂ during photosynthesis to convert inorganic substances into organic matter, and zooplankton and organisms of higher trophic level in turn feed on them. The bacteria decompose debris and excrement of them and convert organic matter in to CO₂ and other inorganic matter. Under specific ocean condition, CO₂ is reversely released from sea-surface to air. Ocean carbon cycle is very important factor for predicting global warming. Numerical model must be used in order to quantitatively and generally estimate physical, chemical and biological transport and correlations. Since 1990s, based on the approach of Bacastow and Maier-Reimer (1990) and Sarmiento et al. (1992), ocean carbon cycle model has been developed and improved by many researchers. Although initially ocean carbon circulation models were very simple, vertical, one-dimensional and box model type with only physical factor, recently the models are becoming three-dimensional, and physical models are usually combined with biological model. However a number of conventional studies used ocean carbon cycle model attempted to estimate phytoplankton biomass and net primary production (NPP), focused on only euphotic zone (within 200m depth of the upper ocean). Even though the mean ocean depth is about 3800m, the greater part of ocean area are twilight zone (about 200 ~ 1000m) and deeper zone. Biogeochemically each phytoplankton species have various functions viz. silicification, calcification and N₂ fixation. Photosynthesis and NPP carried out by different phytoplankton functional groups may be different and may influence on exchange of CO₂ between air and sea-surface and also higher ecosystem differently. In a number of conventional studies phytoplankton is separated based on the phytoplankton size, however attention was not paid to separation of plankton groups based on the functional types. But it is very important to consider plankton functional types for analysis of ocean carbon cycle using numerical model focused on deep sea. In this study, we mainly estimated lower ecosystem, zooplankton biomass in deep sea using new ocean carbon cycle model with additional plankton functional types. We noticed that a conventional model focused on phytoplankton and NPP underestimated the zooplankton biomass in deep sea. However, we improved the model and estimated the zooplankton biomass in deep sea significantly better than the estimated derived from the conventional models.

P-29

Indian Beamline at Photon Factory

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High brilliance, polarization, coherence and energy tunability of x-ray synchrotron sources made it almost inevitable for the investigation of structural, chemical and magnetic properties of the nanomaterials. An 'Indian Beamline' is being developed at BL18B of Photon Factory synchrotron radiation facility, Japan. The Indian beamline (BL18B) is using the existing beamline optics and setting up various instruments to make it multipurpose beamline for materials research. With its full capacity this beamline will be covering five different areas of present days x-ray synchrotron research as: (a) Powder diffraction from nanocrystals at various sample environments like high pressure, wide range of temperature and different chemical environments. (b) Diffraction from single crystals and epitaxial multilayers. (c) X-ray reflectivity and diffuse scattering from solid and liquid surfaces or interfaces. (d) In-situ growth and structural characterization of thin films and nanostructures using dedicated UHV system and (e) Small angle x-ray scattering (SAXS) from bulk materials and interfaces. Presently, we are running in limited capacity and can do experiments like powder diffraction at high pressure (maximum ~ 30 GPa) and temperature down to 10K, single crystal diffraction from epitaxial multilayer's and nanocrystals, x-ray reflectivity and diffuse scattering from solid surfaces in inert gas atmosphere.

In this paper, we will report some diffraction data taken at Indian Beamline to characterize aligned ZnO nanorods grown on sapphire substrate by a chemical vapour deposition technique. The x-ray diffraction data of aligned ZnO nanorods showed very strong (002) wurtzite peak of ZnO indicating c-axis growth, which in this case lie along the length of the nanowires. We also measured high-resolution single crystal diffraction, specular X-ray reflectivity and diffuse scattering measurements on MBE grown SiGe epitaxial layers. The results of a 10 bilayer Si/Ge multilayer structure grown on Si (001) substrate with a growth temperature of 400°C, rate of deposition of Si and Ge was kept as 1Å/s and 0.5Å/s respectively will be presented here.

P-30

Nanomaterials As Growth Enhancers of Rice Plants

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Application of nanomaterials in agriculture plays a pilot role in transforming and shaping modern agriculture. Plants provide a potential pathway for the transport of nanoparticles; however the major concern is the ecotoxicological effects of nanomaterials. Although plants occupy a major role in ecosystem, only limited works are focusing on the effects of translocated nanoparticles on plant growth and metabolic functions⁽¹⁻³⁾. Hence there is greater scope to understand the interaction of engineered nanoparticles with plant system which could be utilized for their immense applications in plant biology. We studied the effects of carbon based nanomaterials (SWCNTs and MWCNTs) and magnetic nanoparticles on the germination and growth of rice plants, which is the staple food for more than half of the human population. We observed an enhanced germination and improved growth of the treated plants compared to the control plants. Such positive responses open up wider opportunities for the use of such nanomaterials as growth enhancers and as mediators of various delivery methods in plants.

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Nanoparticles in Ethnic medicines of India

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Nowadays, metal nanoparticles are getting lots of attractions in the biomedical field because of their specificity and curing of certain diseases. Among the metal nanoparticles gold and silver have a history of using them in various drug formulations.

Recent advances in gold and silver nanoparticles research and their applications in the biomedical field inspired us to analyze one of the ayurvedic drugs, Suvarnnadi Gulika (Suvarnnadi – Gold and other materials, Gulika- Tablet) to find out its nanoparticle history. Many Indian books on holistic medicines already described the importance of Suvarnnadi or Suvarnamukthadi tablets due to the presence of noble metals in drug formulations. Suvarnamukthadi gulika is one of the major medications in Ayurveda prescribed by many physicians for brain disorders like stroke and other cerebrovascular disorders. Here we report the various nanostructures, which we found in the analysis of Suvarnamukthadi tablet to show the history of nanotechnology in Indian ethnical medical preparations. For the detailed analysis of Suvarnamukthadi gulika, TEM and EDS mapping is conducted. The size of gold and silver nanoparticles was between 5-50 nm. This result clearly shows the efficiency of suvarnnadi Gulika is partly due to the presence of nanoparticulate system.

P-32**Anti-aging Activity In The Ashwagandha Leaf Extract**

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Ashwagandha (*Withania somnifera*) is extensively used in Indian traditional system of home medicine (Ayurveda) to promote physical and mental health. Although sheltered by long history of its use, laboratory evidence of its health promoting activities is lacking. We initially used combined chemical and functional analyses using *in vitro* cell based gene-silencing assays and assigned anticancer activity of Ashwagandha leaf extract (i-Extract) to Withanone. We found that whereas cancer cells were killed by Ashwagandha extract, normal human cells were not affected and even looked healthier in the culture. Based on these findings, we speculated that the Ashwagandha derived-phytochemicals may be recruited for anti-aging, protection from oxidative damage, accumulated molecular lesions. We found that Withanone feeding to normal cells extended their lifespan and this was supported by the molecular assays that provided evidence that Withanone protected the cells from oxidative damage and enhanced the activity of “molecular garbage recycle” machinery. To the best of our knowledge, we provide the first example of phytochemical that has anti-cancer and anti-aging activity and hence could be recruited for safe and functional therapy for old age.

P-33**Mode Shift In The Indian Ocean Climate Through 20th Century
Recorded In Coral IOD Index**

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The Indian Ocean Dipole (IOD), an oscillation of sea surface temperatures in the Indian Ocean, has become a major influence on the weather variations in the Indian Ocean region. During positive IOD events, abnormally warm sea surface temperatures in the western Indian Ocean are accompanied by severe droughts over the Indonesian region and heavy rainfall over east Africa. To learn more about IOD patterns, we studied a 115-year coral record from Kenya. We analyzed coral oxygen isotope ratios, which trace rainfall anomalies, to reconstruct IOD variability. The results add to evidence that IOD has been occurring more frequently in recent decades. We found that before 1924, IOD occurred approximately every 10 years, but since 1960, IOD events have been occurring approximately 18 months to 3 years apart. The mode shift has also coincided with an intensified coupling with Indian summer monsoon rainfall. We suggest that global warming effects on the western Indian Ocean have driven the observed shift in IOD variability, and note that the IOD has replaced the El Nino/Southern Oscillation (ENSO) as the major driver of climate patterns over the Indian Ocean region.

P-34**Withanone, A Natural Antidote For Industrial Chemical Induced Bio-Toxicity**

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Present day lifestyle heavily depends on the industrial products that pose a variety of health risks in a direct and indirect way. One of these is the bio-toxicity of industrial chemicals and their metabolites. Ester phthalates are a class of industrial chemicals used in a large variety of consumer products including variety of household products (building materials, plastic objects, textiles, adhesives, paints and deodorants), food and personal care products including agricultural adjuvant, pesticides, cosmetics and perfumes, electronics (coatings, stabilizers and surfactants) and pharmaceuticals (enteric coating of oral pills, viscosity control agents, surfactants and stabilizers). Globally, more than 18 billion pounds of ester phthalates are used annually and toxicity of these chemicals occurs through ingestion, inhalation, intravenous injection and dermal exposure on a daily basis. MAA, a common metabolite of ester phthalates has been shown to cause physical, reproductive, skeletal and hematopoietic abnormalities in rat test models. Many Ester phthalates (Monoethyl phthalate, monobutyl phthalate, monobenzyl phthalate) have been detected in house dust and in urine specimens from pregnant and lactating women living in New York City. These reports have raised the requirement of search and development of reagents that could protect the bio-systems from Industrial toxins. We report that steroidal lactone Withanone from Ashwagandha (an Ayurvedic herb) protected normal human cells from MAA-induced damage and extended their health-span. Withanone and Withanone-rich Ashwagandha is a strong candidate for health food industry.

P-35**Wind Disaster Detection From Satellite And Aerial Imageries Using Wavelet Feature Extraction And Latest Pattern Recognition Techniques**

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Damages on building structures due to wind have increased worldwide during the past few decades. Speedy identification of such damaged structures and faster relief measures will reduce the impact of such disasters. The progress in Space Technology in the past few years provides high-resolution satellite and aerial imageries. These imageries could be used effectively to facilitate faster relief works, mostly in the remote areas, where a field survey is difficult to accomplish. In this research, funded by MEXT, Japan, through the Global Center of Excellence Program, 2008-2013, the identification of wind damaged buildings is performed using the latest cutting edge tools in feature extraction; Wavelets and pattern recognition tools such as Artificial Neural Network (ANN) and Support Vector Machine (SVM), and there by categorizing into different damaged scales, so that immediate aid can be provided depending on the requirement. In this paper, satellite imageries of Punta Gorda, United States, before and after the Hurricane 'Charley' disaster in 2004 and aerial images, before and after tornado damages at Saroma, Japan in 2006, are exploited for wind damaged building identification. Wavelet features are extracted and the best features, which are capable of separating damaged buildings from non-damaged and partially damaged, are selected using decision tree method. Identification and classification is done using ANN and SVM and the results are compared.

P-36

Anti Tumor Efficacy of DACHPt-loaded Micelles Against Orthotopic Gastric Cancer

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Chemotherapy that uses nanocarriers has been developed to improve the clinical treatment of solid tumors by obtaining high accumulation of drugs in tumor tissues but limited accumulation in normal organs. However, despite the urgent need for effective chemotherapy for intractable solid tumors, including diffuse-type gastric carcinoma¹, nanocarriers of any design have not been successful yet in exhibiting significant therapeutic effects on these cancers.

Recently, polymeric micelles have received considerable attention as a promising modality of drug delivery systems^{2,3}. It has been demonstrated that polymeric micelles could circulate stably in the bloodstream and, therefore, accumulate effectively in the solid tumor due to the EPR (Enhanced Permeability and Retention) effect⁴. Thus, polymeric micelle-based drug carriers might possess several unique advantages, including: (a) the applicability to use a variety of therapeutic agents (b) high drug loading capacity; and (c) controlled drug release.

The polymeric micelles incorporating the (1,2 diaminocyclohexane) platinum(II) (DACHPt), the parent complex of the anticancer drug oxaliplatin, were prepared through the polymer-metal complexation of DACHPt with poly(ethylene glycol)-b-poly(glutamic acid) [PEG-b-P(Glu)]. The resultant micelles were evaluated *in vivo* for the antitumor activity against OCUM-2MLN orthotopic tumors. DACHPt-loaded micelles (DACHPt/m) were approximately 30 nm in diameter and had a narrow size distribution. The micelles were shown improved antitumor activity against orthotopic gastric cancer tumors. Biodistribution studies have shown greater tumor accumulation with micelles than oxaliplatin or control group. These data suggest that DACHPt/m could be a promising formulation for the treatment of intractable of solid tumors.

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P-37**Preparation of the LiMPO₄ (M=Fe, Mn)/Graphene Nanocrystalline Electrodes by Supercritical Ethanol Process and their Electrochemical Properties**

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Progress in the colloidal synthesis of high quality nanocrystals have opened up new possible routes to address the challenges of fabricating low cost, high efficiency energy materials. In particular, lithium ion battery materials based on the olivine structured LiMPO₄ have recently been proposed as potential candidates for high energy and high rate applications such as hybrid electric vehicles and electric vehicles. The ability to control the homogeneity in size, shape, composition, crystal structure and surface nature of the nanocrystals is crucial for overcoming their intrinsic problems. Although many efforts have been made on controlling LiMPO₄ nanocrystal size, morphology and crystal structure via wet chemistry, the difficulty in producing LiMPO₄ below 30 nm is hampering the realization of critical size for these cathode material, where nano size effect will be significant. We report a facile method to synthesize olivine structured nanocrystals with controlled size, morphology by supercritical ethanol process. This process has some obvious advantages; process is simple and fast, reaction can be performed in one-pot at low temperature (250-400°C) in short (4-15 min) reaction time; the size and morphology can be easily controlled by using oleylamine as both capping and reducing agent. The nanocrystals are highly crystalline and aggregation free. We have studied effect of different reaction conditions such as reaction time, temperature, precursor concentration and precursor to surfactant ratio on the nano size. Considering the low cost Li ion battery, we developed low temperature conductive coating method by mixing with PEDOT/graphene at room temperature. The surfactant coated on the LiMPO₄ nanocrystals was removed by washing with tetramethylammonium hydroxide before mixing with conductive materials. In order to get high rate performance LiMPO₄ nanocrystals were coated with CNT and AB under ball milling followed by heat treatment at 600°C under argon atmosphere.

P-38**El Niño Modoki In The Equatorial Pacific And The Anomalous Climatic Conditions During The Summer And Winters of 2009-10**

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During the summer (Jun-Sep; JJAS) of 2009 and the winter (Dec-Feb;DJF) of 2009-10, the equatorial Pacific sea surface temperature (SST) was anomalously positive. During JJAS, the spatial pattern of the SST was a mixture of the El Niño and the recently discovered El Niño Modoki pattern, but the winter SST pattern was that of the El Niño Modoki. During the JJAS of 2009, the Indian subcontinent suffered one of the worst droughts with a seasonal deficit of 23%. The winters (DJF) of 2009-10 were warmer over the Canada, Greenland and anomalously cooler over the USA and Europe. Our study using a Global Atmospheric General Circulation model shows that most of the observed climatic anomalies observed during the summer of 2009 and winter of 2009-10 were due to the El Niño Modoki conditions prevailing in the central Pacific. Our study shows that the El Niño Modoki induced subsidence in the west Pacific simulates Rossby waves from the western Pacific to sub-tropics with rising motions nearer the Indian latitudes. This rising motion in turn induces a zonal circulation with sinking motion over the Indian subcontinent causing drought like conditions over India. Our study also shows that during the winter of 2009-10 most of the climatic anomalies over the Southern Hemisphere and the southern parts of North America were due to the El Niño Modoki conditions in the central Pacific.

P-39**The Effect of Bound Water Molecules on Binding Orientations
In CDK2 Inhibitors**

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The Cyclin-dependent kinase 2 (CDK2) is a serine/threonine protein kinase that plays a key role in the cell cycle control system. CDK2 inhibitors containing the related pyrazolopyrimidines and imidazopyrazines are discovered through high-throughput screening. Pyrazolopyrimidines inhibitors have shown a common binding mode feature as other purine based inhibitors with CDK2. In common binding mode the purine core forms two hydrogen bonds with the backbone of the kinase hinge region. But imidazopyrazines have shown a special binding mode compare to other purine based inhibitors. To understand the origin of the difference in pyrazolopyrimidine and imidazopyrazine binding modes with CDK2, we then proceeded to investigate in detail with presence of bound water molecules. For that, we have used molecular docking, molecular dynamics and free energy calculations to analyze the interactions between the inhibitor, CDK2 and water. We have determined that the water molecules have a significant role on inhibitors binding orientation in CDK2. Complex structures obtained by Autodock have shown that the rare binding mode only occur when bound water molecules are present. We have also determined in MD simulation that binding between CDK2 and inhibitor was dependent on the number of bound water molecules. Cluster analysis also identified water sites conserved in CDK2, providing a list of water sites that may contribute to ligand discrimination. After locating the hydration sites we conclude that these water molecules have a significant role on ligand binding orientations in CDK2.

P-40**Development of A Vortex Flow Generator and Investigations on Pressure Acting on Building Models in Tornado Like Flow**

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Tornadoes are earth's extreme local weather disturbances that involve very complex interaction between wind and man-made structures. The real time investigations on the occurrence and mechanism of tornado are impractical because of the inherent danger and unpredictability associated with the phenomenon. This demands creating an analogous situation in laboratory to understand the mechanics of flow under such complex regimes. A *Tornado Simulator* was developed in the Wind Engineering Research Centre at Tokyo Polytechnic University. The simulator develops a rotating vortex flow, analogues to the nature's vortices. The required angular momentum is imparted by vanes kept on the periphery. Velocity field in the turbulent core and the surrounding periphery is measured at definite heights and at various radial locations. Scaled models of buildings are placed at definite positions in the floor of simulator and pressure distribution on the cube faces and on floor are obtained. An attempt is made to quantitatively and qualitatively discuss the salient features of the tornado like flow and the characteristics of the wind loads developed on the buildings based on dynamic and geometric parameters governing the flow. Flow visualization results using a green laser arrangement gives an insight into the mechanism of the flow.

P-41**Impact of IOD/ENSO at a Catchment Scale**

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The climatology of stream-flow at the Nanjung gauge station of the Citarum River in Indonesia shows significant flow during November to April and very less flow during June-September. The variation in this seasonal stream-flow significantly affects the human population. So, it is important to understand the underlying mechanisms that cause that variation. Since the variability of climatic conditions in the tropical Indian and Pacific Oceans are main driver of the rainfall variability over the Maritime Continent, their roles in river stream-flow is explored in this study. A scientific analysis is made to link the stream-flow variability with the rainfall and SST variations over the Indian and Pacific Oceans on daily time scale. The observed discharge data from 1974-2008 (35 years) at the Nanjung station, the down most outlet of the upper catchment, shows a strong correlation with the Indian Ocean Dipole (IOD) and the El Nino/Southern Oscillation (ENSO) events. In the boreal fall, just before the peak in the seasonal rainy season, the stream-flow was considerably affected by the IOD induced dry conditions. Many of the low stream flow events were associated with positive IOD events. On the other hand, rainy conditions associated with La Nina gave rise to high stream-flow events during the season. In the boreal winter, the low-stream-flow events were dominantly caused by El Nino conditions that suppress the seasonal rainfall over Java and Sumatra.

P-42**A New Biomarker For Metal Contamination In Water**

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The industrial revolution has taken man to the great heights but at the same time raised several environmental issues worldwide. The industries produce waste and dump it into water bodies and affect the environment and physiology of both flora and fauna living therein. The waste includes heavy metals and toxic chemicals. Every living organisms including several plants and fish are very sensitive to the change in their habitat and such change in their environment triggers the upregulation of certain proteins. These upregulated proteins can be harnessed to detect the water pollution in the water bodies and can act as sensitive biomarker(s) for the detection of environmental pollution. One such set of proteins that are upregulated in response to variety of stress conditions are Heat Shock Proteins (HSPs). Mortalin is one of the members of the heat shock protein 70 family and is found to be upregulated in several stress conditions including cancers. In the present study, we hypothesized that mortalin may be upregulated in response to chemical stresses including heavy metals and hence may serve as a sensitive biomarker for environmental pollution. To test this hypothesis we used *Oryzia Latipes* (Japanese killfish) as a model, which is also known to have similarity to many human diseases. Medaka was reared in tap water and was treated with different concentrations of heavy metals (cadmium sulfate, nickle chloride and arsenic trioxide) and toxic chemical (hydrogen peroxide). We demonstrated that the level of mortalin protein in Medaka increases when they experience heavy metal and oxidant stress conditions and hence mortalin can act as a biomarker for water pollution. Also, ELISA could detect the upregulation of protein at nanogram level. Thus, mortalin could act as a sensitive biomarker for detection of environmental pollution.

Cancer Intervention By Ashwagandha Leaf Extract

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Cancer, a multiplex disease that involves genetic, epigenetic and environmental factors, is one of the top two killers of the modern society. In spite of the enormous progress in its understanding and treatment, cancer incidence and complexity seems to be escalating exponentially, and is one of the major challenges in biomedicine and bio-industry. Besides, a large proportion of the global population (underdeveloped and developing world) does not have access to the advanced treatments including medicine and surgery that are either regionally restricted or very expensive. In this scenario, natural ways to prevent and cure cancer have caught worldwide attention. At our end, we explored the anticancer activity in the alcoholic extract of Ashwagandha leaves (i-Extract) by using human cell based proliferation assays and nude mice based tumor assays. We found that the i-Extract and its constituent Withanone kill human cancer cells selectively; normal cells were least affected. Consistently with the *in vitro* assays, *in vivo* assays including subcutaneous xenografts and metastasis models revealed cancer-curing potential of i-Extract and Withanone. In order to understand the molecular mechanism(s) of the anticancer effect of i-Extract and Withanone, we identified their cellular targets and signaling pathways by employing cell based loss-of-function screenings and bioinformatics. We demonstrate that the i-Extract and Withanone inhibit the proliferation of cancer cells by activation of tumor suppressor p53 pathway, inactivation of telomerase (a hallmark of cancer cells) and induction of proteins involved in cell differentiation and adhesion resulting in loss of cancer cell migration (metastasis). We propose Ashwagandha leaf extract and Withanone as effective, cheap and safe anticancer reagents.

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P-44**Hollow Nano-Structures of Metal Chalcogenides via
Solution Phase Sacrificial Template Route**

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Hollow nanostructures have been drawing intense research interest on account of their unique structure-induced optical, electrical, and catalysis properties that may bring a series of opportunities for their applications as photoelectric devices, drug delivery, sensors, chemical catalysis, and solar cells. Various chemical methodologies have been developed to achieve this special structure, either by using removable templates such as silica and carbon spheres, emulsion droplets, micelles, and gas bubbles, or by emulsion droplets directing self-assembly of the primary particles without using external templates and self templates by the Kirkendall effect. The Kirkendall effect, a conventional physical process, has been introduced for the formation of hollow structured materials, where hollow structures are formed due to the generation of vacancies when one species diffuses faster than another through the interface between two components. In this strategy, nanostructures as the source template are partially or completely converted to desired materials without change of the shape.

In the present work, we demonstrate the formation of CdX and ZnX (X=S, Se, and Te) hollow nanostructures via sacrificial route which is simple, inexpensive, feasible for the synthesis in bulk quantities, capable to control the dimensions of the nanostructures, and applicable for large area deposits. The formation of hollow structures such as CdSe hexagonal nanocage, CdSe nanotube^{1,2} and ZnSe nanoparticles has been explored by sacrificial template route and will be discussed in this poster.

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Iron Isotope Effect in Fe-based Superconductors

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The iron-based superconductors are discovered in 2008, set up new high- T_c family and most competitive with cuprate based superconductors. Even though iron based superconductor are challenging materials, the pairing mechanism is under debate, as controversial reports on isotope effects are reported [1,2]. One possible way to elucidate the pairing mechanism is to study the phonon mechanism due to isotope substitution and can be given by the relation, $T_c \sim M^{-a_{Fe}}$ (where M is the Fe isotope mass and a is the isotope coefficient). In this symposium, we demonstrate the most reproducible and reliable iron isotope results in (Ba,K)Fe₂As₂ ($T_c=38$ K) and SmFeAsO_{1-y} (54 K) superconductors. The substitution of iron isotopes represents inverse isotope effect in (Ba,K)Fe₂As₂ [1] (7 set sample average $a_{Fe} = -0.18 \pm 0.03$), while absence of an isotope effect in SmFeAsO_{1-y} (5 set sample average $a_{Fe} = -0.02 \pm 0.01$) [3]. In summary, irrespective of the magnitude of the isotope coefficient, both represent that the pairing mechanism is unconventional and cannot be explained by BCS theory, which assumes phonon as major binding glue.

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P-46**CARF, A Novel Regulator of Cell Proliferation**

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Normal human cells can divide only for a limited number of times in culture whereas the cancer cells can proliferate indefinitely. Human chromosome locus INK4A encodes two independent proteins, ARF and INK4A that are involved in control of cell proliferation. Loss of function of these proteins is frequently associated with a variety of cancers, and hence the knowledge on their regulation and function is an important aspect of cancer understanding and intervention. We undertook a study on the functional regulation of ARF protein and cloned a novel protein that interacts with ARF. We named it CARF for collaborator of ARF. We demonstrate that CARF is an important player of the cell proliferation control of normal and cancer cells. Forced overexpression of CARF induced growth arrest of cancer cells and premature aging of normal cells. CARF depletion leads to cell death that was characterized as aneuploidy and apoptosis. We demonstrate that CARF is a good candidate for cancer therapeutics.

P-47**Nanostructured Materials for Electrochemical Cells**

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Mesoporous materials have received much attention due their large internal surface area and pore volume, tunable and narrow pore diameter^{1,2}, which made them ideal for use in energy conversion and storage devices. In particular, ordered mesoporous carbons are promising as supporting matrix for catalysts in fuel cells, hydrogen storage materials, electrochemical double-layer capacitors, and electrode materials in lithium batteries. The textural parameters of the nanoporous carbon materials are critical in many industrial applications particularly, separation, adsorption and fuel cells. However, a little attention has been given in the studies to the textural parameters control of nanoporous carbon materials. The present study is focused on the preparation of ordered nanoporous carbon using mesoporous silica or metallosilicates as template and sucrose or glucose as a carbon source.

The carbon materials possess well-ordered structure with regular particle size. The specific pore volume is in the range of 0.93-1.51 cm³/g and pore diameter in the range of 1.6-2.3 nm. The specific surface area of mesoporous carbons prepared using glucose as a carbon source are in the range of 1384 m²/g to 2073 m²/g, which is higher than nanoporous carbons prepared using sucrose as a carbon source. The results indicate that the carbon source with a small molecular size is critical to achieve the nanoporous carbon materials with excellent textural characteristics. The textural parameters of nanoporous carbon samples can be finely controlled using glucose as a carbon source. In addition, the electro catalytic activity of the carbon materials has been studied.

It has been found that the charge of hydrogen desorption is dependent on weight% of Pt loaded and textural parameters of mesoporous carbon materials. It has been found that mesoporous carbon shows superior electrochemical performance compared with carbon black due to its large ordered pore channels, which are continuous connected with the large quantity of small pores in the carbon pore walls.

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**Deciphering The Class B Scavenger Receptor, Croquemort From
Kuruma Shrimp *Marsupenaeus Japonicus***

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The scavenger receptor, Croquemort is a member of the CD36 superfamily comprising transmembrane proteins involved in the recognition of polyanionic ligands. It has been proved by various researchers that member of CD36 superfamily are involved in immunity and developmental processes. In the present study, we report a cDNA encoding the kuruma shrimp, *Marsupenaeus japonicus* Croquemort scavenger receptor (MjSCRQB) obtained from the cDNA library of lymphoid organ and RACE amplification. The full length cDNA of 2098 bp contains an open reading frame of 1596 nucleotides that translates into a 532-amino acid putative peptide putative peptide, with a 5' untranslated region of 323 bp and 3' UTR of 153 bp. The MjSCRQB is constitutively expressed in gills, heart, hemolymph, hepatopancreas, intestine, lymphoid organ, muscle, nerve, stomach and in the brain with high value. Expression analysis in lymphoid organs of WSSV post infection revealed the high levels of MjSCRQB in 72 and 120 hrs durations. The MjSCRQB contains putative functional domains including transmembrane domains and CD36 domain. Multiple alignments of MjSCRQB amino acid sequences showed significant identity with DmSCRQB (31%), SsSCRQB (29%), HsSCRQB (28%) and RnSCRQB (30%). In the phylogenetic analysis, MjSCRQB is identified in the invertebrate scavenger receptor region. This is the first report in crustacean sector on identification and characterization of Croquemort scavenging receptor, MjSCRQB which may lead to better understanding of the molecular events unexplored in shrimp system.

P-49**Satellite-detected Coccolithophore Blooms in Coastal Waters of Japan**

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Coccolithophores are one of the main groups of marine phytoplankton playing key roles in the marine ecosystem and in marine biogeochemistry. These organisms have drawn considerable attention as they play a unique role in the global carbon cycle because of their combined effects on both the organic carbon and the carbonate pump. Under the present study, several environmental/physical/chemical variables derived from satellite and in situ data sets were used to understand the spatial and temporal variability of coccolithophore abundance in the coastal waters along the coast of Honshu. The 12-year (1997-2009) time-series analysis showed that the combined effect of high solar radiation, decreased temperature and low shallow mixed layer depth significantly contributed to development of coccolithophore bloom. During April-May of 2005, a large coccolithophore bloom was detected in the Enshu-nada area using satellite data, which was found to be the most extensive blooms ever reported in this ocean area. There was a pronounced temperature shift preceding occurrence of this bloom, suggesting that exceptionally large coccolithophore blooms are caused by pronounced environmental conditions and the variability of the physical environment strongly affects the spatial extent of these blooms. Since these blooms are thought to play a key role in biogeochemical cycling and contribute to climate processes, they can have major effect on the oceanic and atmospheric environment of this region.

P-50**Development of Uber Catalytic NO_x Reduction Technologies for Diesel Engines**
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At the global level, with rapid growth in motor vehicle activity and acceleration of urbanization, the amount of pollutants emitting from vehicles is steadily increasing, causing serious energy security and climate change implications. The rapid growth in motor vehicle activity in developing countries has brought in its wake a range of serious socioeconomic, environmental, health, and welfare impacts. Of these impacts, those resulting from air pollution, due to emissions from motor vehicles among other sources, have been the focus of considerable public concern and policy attention. On gasoline vehicles using a three way catalyst technology HC, CO and NO_x are converted to harmless gases. However for diesel vehicles, which are more efficient than gasoline vehicles, catalyst based technologies were found to be inefficient and costly. Furthermore technologies like selective catalytic reduction using aqueous urea solution needs driver intervention making overall operation of the system more expensive and challenging particularly developing countries like India.

To deal with the problem of air pollution from the emission of nitrogen oxides (NO_x) by vehicular engines, especially diesel engines, several technologies such as selective catalytic reduction of NO_x using Urea /NH₃ (NH₃-SCR) or using hydrocarbons (HC-SCR) and NO_x storage reduction (NSR) have been developed for the removal of these undesirable gases under lean conditions. Reducing automotive emissions while increasing the fuel economy of cars requires a robust exhaust aftertreatment solution to meet stringent NO_x emission standards. The objective of “Emission Control and Catalysis Team” at AIST is to develop a very efficient combustion process, alternate fuels that could decrease the carbon foot print and pollutant emissions as well as to develop an uber and cheaper catalytic technology to eliminate these pollutants and meet the regulations at different parts of the world. The poster will present the recent advances in DeNO_x science and technology and also some typical obstacles encountered in the application of these developed technologies and the resulting costs. An overview of our group’s activities will be described.

In spite of a large number of efforts on the catalyst developments for the efficient removal of NO_x, the performance of the SCR catalysts has yet to reach a practical level. This implies that there is a limit to the improvement in SCR performance through the design of the catalyst alone. Work in our group is aimed at developing ways to make the catalysts more effective for a wider operating temperature window while assuring a prolonged catalyst lifetime. We are also investigating different possible ways to make use of the existing exhaust gases as reductant namely, hydrocarbons. To achieve an enhancement in SCR activity, we have adopted new concepts such as reforming of the diesel exhaust gas to regenerate a desirable efficient reductant such as CO and H₂ and also the design of the reaction atmosphere by using dual reductant systems, such as CO + NH₃.

P-51**Dynamic Registration-Area (RA) Selection Based on Cell-crossing Probability**

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Due to rapid growth of cellular mobile communication, but restricted availability of band width, cell sizes continue to decrease resulting in increase in number of cells in a service area. This results in increasing cost of location management, i.e, update and paging cost. Most of the movement takes place along specific road surfaces, and in specific direction depending on time of the day. The aim of the present work is to use a lot of MHs movement information to extract the traffic flow characteristics of the city, and use that information to create dynamic registration area to optimize location management cost.

P-52**Similarity And Difference Between Multi-Band Superconductivity
And Particle Physics**Yasumoto Tanaka

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Since an earth-breaking work of spontaneous symmetry breaking, it has been considered as there is a definite implication that the particle physics and the superconductivity have a close relationship. Examining Bardeen-Cooper-Schrieffer (BCS) theory, Nambu established the basis of the particle physics. The gauge field theory developed in succeeding works such as Weinberg-Salam theory and quantum chromodynamics (QCD) is re-introduced into solid-state physics.

The superconductivity emerged in multi-band superconductors (multi-band superconductivity) gives a proper platform where these gauge field theories comes back. Rather than the symmetry, the multiple internal freedoms are considered as a common property for those gauge field theory and multi-band superconductivity. The internal freedoms can be designed by the nanotechnology and material engineering. Universe accepts only one theory. Un-selected theories are considered as just derivatives as approximations or garbage. The solid-state materials are more tolerant of variations. An electronics developed by a gauge field theory having multiple internal freedoms can have an advantage, which the conventional electronics does not have. The gauge field (which is realized and utilized) in the solid-state device is only electromagnetic field. Because the vacuum accepts the electromagnetic field, any device based on the electromagnetic field suffers from an un-expected coupling to the vacuum and other one through vacuum. When we can introduce "other gauge field", we can design an electro-magnetically silent electronics. There is non-electro-magnetic gauge field such as a color field in the particle physics. To realize a new electronics free from electro-magnetic field, we should understand the gauge field in the multi-band superconductivity.

Of course a concept and knowledge of the particle physics is useful. However understanding of essential difference between the particle physics and multi-band superconductivity is also necessary for design of a new electronics.

This work was supported by the Strategic International Cooperative Program, Japan Science and Technology Agency (JST), by Feasibility Study of the Application of Multiple-Order Parameters in Materials to Information Processing, Department of Science and Technology (India), and by AIST through a grant for overriding priority research from the New Superconducting Revolution program.

Surface Analyses of Electropolished Niobium Samples For Superconducting Radio Frequency Cavity

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The International Linear Collider (ILC) will accelerate electron and positron beams to high energy of 250x250 GeV CM. To achieve such a high energy, ILC will require more than 15,000 superconducting radio frequency (SRF) cavities. The E-field gradient per cavity should be higher as much as possible to built cheaper and shorter ILC. Niobium (Nb) is the main material used for fabricating such SRF cavities. The manufacturing of a cavity from Nb ingots includes many processes and the possibility of inclusion of contaminants at each step is therefore enhanced. After a cavity is produced, cavity inner surface is polished with several methods to get smooth and clean surface. The electropolishing (EP) is adopted worldwide as a final surface treatment method for Nb cavities for ILC. As a side effect of EP process, some contaminants might appear on the cavity surface. These contaminants might be the sources of field emission when a high electric field is excited in a SRF cavity and limit the cavity performance. EP facility at STF (KEK) uses same EP acid mixture many times (up to Nb concentration of 8 gm/l), which enhances the possibility of such contaminants on the surface after the EP process. In order to study the aging effect of EP acid on contaminants presence on the cavity surface and the distribution of such contaminants at different positions of cavity, two experiments were conducted by using fresh EP acid solution and aged EP acid solution with niobium concentration of 7.9 g/l. For the experiment, a real single cell Nb cavity was drilled with six holes of same diameter as that of the samples at three typical positions, namely “equator,” “iris” and “beam pipe”. Then, this cavity assembled with six samples was electropolished with fresh EP acid in the first experiment and with aged EP acid solution in another experiment followed by rinsing with ultra pure water. After the EP process, all samples were carefully detached from the cavity in the clean room and EPed surfaces were analyzed by x-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) with depth profiling. The surfaces of samples were also observed by scanning electron microscope (SEM). According to the XPS analysis results, no sulfur and fluorine were found on the surfaces treated by fresh EP acid solution within the detection limit of our XPS while remarkable quantity of the sulfur (up to 7 at. %) and fluorine (up to 4 at. %) were present at the surfaces processed by using aged EP. The XPS results also confirmed the chemical state of sulfur was in oxidation state. Sulfur was found maximum at the surface of the sample fixed at the iris position and minimum at the surface of the beam pipe sample. The SEM observations showed that all the surfaces were smooth and covered with many particles of several submicrometers whereas high density of the particles was observed in case of sample surface treated with aged EP acid. Further study is necessary to find the suitable EP conditions to get contaminant-free surface. with the pressure of 15 MPa with a dose of 7.9 l/cm².

P-54

Bottom-Up And Top-Down Approaches Estimated That The Global Ocean Sinks As Large As ~ 2 Giga Tonne Grams of Carbon on Each Year From The Atmosphere

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We have estimated the global oceanic absorption of green house gases, namely Carbondioxide (CO₂), using two independent approaches. In the first approach, a global ocean bio-geochemical general circulation model is employed in which the circulation and chemical processes of bio-geochemical elements in the ocean are numerically simulated. The model-predicted CO₂ concentrations in the surface oceans are then constrained with a quarter-a-million of ship-based observations by making use of mathematical data assimilation principles. The model and the data-assimilation suggested that the total absorption of CO₂ gas by the global ocean has contributed to sink as large as 2 Giga tonne grams of carbon from the atmosphere between June-2009 and April-2010. In the second approach, we used the atmospheric CO₂ concentration measurements made from space by the on-board instrument attached to the Greenhouse Gas Observing Satellite (GOSAT) which is launched and operating by Japanese Space Exploration Agency (JAXA) and National Institute for Environmental Studies (NIES). The atmospheric CO₂ measurements made by GOSAT are used to constrain an atmospheric chemical transport model and then inversely estimated the oceanic absorptions and emissions of CO₂ gas. The second approach suggested that global oceans absorbed about 2.5 Giga tonne grams of Carbon between June-2009 and April-2010 from the atmosphere. Using the above two approaches, we uniquely monitor the CO₂ absorptions by the ocean in a near-real-time basis. The ocean model, atmospheric model and assimilation algorithms are originally developed in NIES. The project results and publications can be found in http://www-cger.nies.go.jp/climate/person/valsala/e_index.html.

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Enhancement of Glucose Sensing Behavior of Cobalt Tetraporphyrin (CoTpp) Thin Film By Using Single Wall Carbon Nanotubes (SWCNTs)

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An effective biosensor for the detection of glucose is very important for the clinical diagnosis of diabetes and quality control in food industry. The unique properties of carbon nanotubes (CNTs) such as electrical conductivity, large surface area and mechanical properties make it promising for sensing applications¹. In electrochemical reactions, CNTs have the ability to promote electron transfer between the reaction center and electrode. Plasma polymerized thin films formed in plasma in the vapor phase can be used as interfacial design in biosensors. The surface of these films has good affinity for biological components and offers a suitable interface between biomolecules and electrodes². We have developed a glucose biosensor based on single wall carbon nanotubes (SWCNTs) and cobalt tetraphenylporphine (CoTPP) thin film using glucose oxidase (GOx) enzyme. The use of SWCNTs along with plasma polymerized thin film of CoTPP on indium-doped tin oxide (ITO) electrodes shows enhanced glucose sensing property than devices without SWCNTs. The presence of SWCNTs with plasma polymerized CoTPP polymer enhances the electron transfer between enzyme and ITO substrate that resulted in higher glucose sensing response. The effect of radiofrequency power of plasma for deposition of CoTPP polymer towards sensing of glucose was also studied and found that the sensitivity of these devices increases while decreasing the plasma power.

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P-56**MARCH10 is a Microtubule-Associated E3 Ubiquitin Ligase of Developing Sperm Flagella**

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Mammalian spermatogenesis is a very complex, well-coordinated process that involves the formation of male gametes (spermatozoa) from spermatogonia. Recent discoveries have pointed out the importance of ubiquitination during spermatogenesis. However, the mechanisms involved in this have not been clearly elucidated. Here we identified a novel RING-finger type E3 ubiquitin ligase, namely membrane-associated RING-CH (MARCH) 10, which is highly expressed in the testis of rats. Immunohistochemistry of rat testis showed that MARCH10 expression is upregulated in elongating spermatids but is absent in mature spermatozoa. The immunostaining was localized in the cytoplasm and the principal piece of elongating spermatids. Further analysis done through Immunoelectron microscopy revealed that MARCH10 is present in the fibrous sheath component of the developing flagella. We also observed that the MARCH10 RING-finger domain exhibited an E3 ligase activity in the presence of the ubiquitin-conjugating enzyme UBE2B or UBE2D3. These results suggest that MARCH10 may be involved in the formation of the sperm flagellum.

P-57**Study of Mitochondrial Physiology Using Raman Spectroscopy**Venkatesh Kaliaperumal¹, Hiro-o Hamaguchi^{1,2}

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Mitochondria are an important organelle that controls various functions of biological cells in higher organisms. Mitochondrial dysfunction is implicated in aging and also in several chronic diseases. Conventionally most of the studies are done on fixed cells or fractionated cells. Understanding of the mitochondrial function in living cells is essential to unravel the molecular basis of aging and age related diseases. Our observations using Raman spectroscopy in the study of mitochondrial functions in living yeast cells will be discussed.

P-58**Mortalin Protein In Human Cancers**Tomoko Yaguchi, Ran Gao, Renu Wadhwa, Sunil Kaul

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Hsp70 family protein, mortalin, is an essential chaperone that has been shown to be present in various subcellular sites including mitochondria, plasma membrane, ER and cytosol. It is overexpressed in a variety of cancers and its forced overexpression in cancer cells results in their malignant transformation including higher colony forming efficiency and faster mobility in cell transformation and cell invasion assays, respectively. In nude mice assays, cells overexpressing mortalin formed aggressive tumors and exhibited very high degree of metastasis as compared to control cells. We demonstrate that mortalin translocates to the nucleus and interacts with telomerase that is activated in large majority of the cancers. Mortalin-telomerase interaction leads to activation of telomerase function and promotes cancer.

P-59**The Formation Mechanism of Thick Cloud Band Over Sea of Okhotsk**

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During cold-air outbreaks in the East Asian winter-monsoon season a thick cloud band appears over sea of Okhotsk along the north face of Hokkaido Island, which causes heavy snowfall locally. Numerical simulations were performed to investigate the underline mechanism of the formation and evolution of that cloud band with a high-resolution (0.1° horizontal grid spacing) hydrostatic regional cloud model (RegCM) for the month of January 2003. The simulations were able reproduce the observed cloud band from the satellite images. It is observed that north-western winds from the northern sea of Japan, after reaching Hokkaido island turn towards left due to the topographical effect and becomes almost westerlies with decrement (about 30%) in the wind speed. Whereas the north westerlies becomes northerlies over the Sakhalin island and joins with the turning winds and causes the formation of a convergence zone along the downstream over sea of Okhotsk starting from the cleft between the two islands. Prevailing northerlies which are relatively warm and moist from the Sakhalin island were uplifted along the convergence zone was found reason for the formation of the thick cloud band.

P-60**Plasmalemma H⁺-ATPase Regulates BNIs Release From Sorghum Roots**

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The ability to suppress soil nitrification by releasing inhibitors from roots, a plant function termed 'biological nitrification inhibition' (BNI). Among food crops, sorghum showed significant BNI-capacity. Presence of NH₄⁺ in the root environment of sorghum roots reported to stimulate BNIs release. Here we test the hypothesis that release of BNIs from sorghum roots is powered by plasma membrane H⁺-ATPase activity, functionally linked to NH₄⁺ uptake. Sorghum *cv.* 'Hybrid Sorgo' is grown hydroponically with (NH₄)₂SO₄ or KNO₃ as N source for 3 weeks. Root exudates are collected using aerated solutions of 1mM NH₄⁺ or NO₃⁻ for 4 h and the BNI activity was assayed using bioluminescent *Nitrosomonas*. Root plasma membrane is isolated using a two-phase partitioning system; hydrolytic H⁺-ATPase activity is determined by measuring P_i release after 30 min hydrolysis reaction. The expression of sorghum plasma membrane H⁺ ATPase were analyzed by real time PCR. Our results indicate that both plasma membrane H⁺-ATPase and BNI, released from roots, showed higher activity under NH₄⁺ treatment than NO₃⁻ treatment. This higher activity of H⁺ ATPase is attributed to the higher expression of ATPase genes at transcriptional level. *In vivo*, fusicoccin, a fungal toxin, which can stimulate plasma membrane H⁺-ATPase, showed a strong stimulatory effect on BNI release from roots, even in the absence of NH₄⁺ in the root environment. Also, vanadate, a specific ATPase inhibitor, suppressed the release of BNI from sorghum roots, even in the presence of NH₄⁺ in the root environment. We hypothesize that root plasmalemma H⁺-ATPase activity provides the driving force for the release of BNI and directly regulates BNI release from sorghum roots.

SL-01

Energy Education in Kyoto University Under Global COE Program

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From 2008 in Kyoto University, a Global COE (Center of Excellence) program named “Energy Science in the Age of Global Warming - Toward CO₂ Zero-emission Energy System” has been implemented. Under this program, we intend to establish an international education and research platform to foster educators, researchers, and policy makers who can develop technologies and propose policies for establishing a scenario toward a CO₂ zero-emissions society no longer dependent on fossil fuels, by the year 2100.

In this Global COE program, students are expected to acquire the faculty to understand the comprehensive “energy system” through participation in scenario planning and interaction with researchers from other fields, and apply it to their own research. This approach is expected to become a major feature of human resources cultivation. For Energy Science Research toward no CO₂ emission, we targeted at Renewable Energy (Solar Energy and Biomass Energy), Advanced Nuclear Energy (Fission and Fusion), and Socio-economic Study of Energy. Kyoto university can provide the opportunity for the students to be involved in the advanced research environment on this emerging technology field of energy.

In Kyoto University, Graduate School of Energy Science, Institute of Advanced Energy, Department of Nuclear Engineering, and Research Reactor Institute have jointly established special education course for doctoral students by scenario study, group study, field research, and internship in various institutes.

The fundamental principle of the GCOE Unit for Energy Science Education is to foster a human resource with: 1) comprehensive ability and profound knowledge regarding the energy and environmental issues, 2) capability to organize a research group for the intended research, 3) an international perspective, a communication ability, and a world-class standard research ability, and 4) potential to contribute in solving the energy and environmental issues. For this purpose, students are involved in the cutting edge research activities with latest facilities and knowledge base, together with various support systems. Adding to the regular research activities by individuals, group research on the social aspects of the energy encourages students to work together, with members from different countries. This program is open for foreign students that already occupy the significant fraction of our graduate school students.

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